

Visible light sensitive bismuth vanadate for energy, environmental, and catalytic applications

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ABSTRACT: To achieve the net zero emission dream, developing green and sustainable materials and processes to extract energy and address environmental issues is paramount. Recently, the production of green hydrogen through light-assisted methods has attracted the attention of scientists and researchers. However, the design and development of semiconducting materials with suitable band structures to utilize solar spectrum, high stability, and low cost are significant roadblocks. Among various materials, bismuth vanadate (BiVO_4) is emerging as a low-cost, visible-light-active, and easy-to-synthesize material. This review highlights the unique features of BiVO_4 , such as its structural, electronic, and optical properties, which define its role in hydrogen production through photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical water splitting. Later, we outlined how BiVO_4 and its derivatives can be used for wastewater treatment in the textile, pharmaceutical, and chemical industries. The impact of morphological and structural properties of photocatalytic BiVO_4 in microbial inactivation, N_2 fixation, and CO_2 reduction has also been comprehensively explored. The review concludes with strategies to mitigate photo-corrosion and provides future directions for using BiVO_4 in clean energy and environmental applications.

KEYWORDS: bismuth vanadate, CO_2 and N_2 reduction, hydrogen production, photocatalysis

1 Introduction

The production of sustainable hydrogen as a clean, ecologically friendly alternative energy source is one of the key goals of water splitting. In addition, processes such as photocatalytic (PC) water splitting, CO_2 reduction, nitrogen fixation, and degradation of pollutants using a green approach are pivotal for sustainable

development. PC water oxidation is a multielectron transport and thermodynamically uphill process that includes surface reaction, light absorption, charge generation, separation, and interaction of these charges with the water molecules or reaction intermediates [1]. This PC behavior can be extended to other processes like wastewater treatment and CO_2 reduction. Photocatalytic activity using semiconductor nanomaterials has attracted the scientific community's attention and has the potential to compete with existing technologies [2].

Nanomaterial semiconductors like titanium dioxide (TiO_2), bismuth vanadate (BiVO_4), zinc oxide (ZnO), etc., reveal significant applications in material chemistry. The choice of material for such applications should be such that they are non-toxic, earth-abundant, commercially viable, and scalable [3]. Also, increasing

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efforts are being undertaken by different governments and research groups to design, implement, and fund policies that target replacing expensive and fossil-based materials with abundant and cleaner ones [4]. Amongst various groups of compounds, the role of bismuth-based materials is becoming increasingly significant in photocatalysis. The choice of such compounds is inherently due to their non-toxic nature, optimal energy bandgaps, and higher thermal and chemical stabilities. The growing interest in the design and development of BiVO₄-based materials can be understood from Fig. 1. It represents a yearly pattern of the number of publications related to BiVO₄ in the Scopus search tool. It is worth noting that in the last 10 years, the number of published articles pertaining to BiVO₄ has grown almost 10 times, which is significant. Figure 2 also gives a historical insight into some of the landmark developments in BiVO₄ for different applications.

In the past few years, few reviews have been published to highlight the growing importance of BiVO₄-based materials for different applications like photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting [33–36], photocatalytic water treatment [37, 38], degradation of organic compounds [39, 40], etc. However, most reviews are limited to a few applications, and none discuss the emerging field of CO₂ reduction or photocatalytic bacterial inactivation and N₂ fixation. This review systematically highlights the importance of BiVO₄ for photocatalytic and PEC processes and environmental remediation techniques like degradation of dyes, pharmaceutical and organic compounds, and CO₂ reduction. The

paper also highlights different crystal and electronic structures of BiVO₄ and how these properties contribute effectively to improve the performance of the materials. BiVO₄ exists in three crystal structures: tetragonal dreyerite, orthorhombic pucherite, and monoclinic clinobisvanite. Among these phases, only the monoclinic phase is thermodynamically stable and exhibits good photocatalytic behavior [41]. Thus, the growing importance of BiVO₄-based compounds is primarily due to their narrow bandgap,

Figure 1 The number of publications related to BiVO₄ from 2011 to the present (“BiVO₄” was searched in the Scopus search documents tool, and the data was accessed on 31st Dec 2024).

Figure 2 The timeline for landmark developments in BiVO₄ and its applications [5–32].

better response to exciting narrow light, high photostability, low production cost, etc. Nanostructured BiVO_4 exhibits enhanced properties compared to its bulk counterpart, including a significantly increased surface area, a higher density of catalytically active sites, and distinct electronic and structural characteristics [42]. These features collectively contribute to improved performance in catalytic and PEC applications. Also, BiVO_4 nanomaterials can be synthesized by various well-established processes such as hydrothermal (HT), sol-gel (SG), electrospinning (ES), thermal decomposition (TD), microwave method (MW), etc. [43]. It has the potential to be coupled with a wide range of materials, including carbon-based compounds, oxides, chalcogenides, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), etc. Therefore, the study of the performance of BiVO_4 -doped compounds on photocatalytic degradation of industrial dyes, textile effluent, pharmaceutical wastes, harmful organic compounds, bacterial inactivation, etc., is explained in detail. Due to the increasing energy demand, energy production, such as fossil fuels and non-renewable energy sources, is depleted daily, resulting in global warming. Hence, to reduce this and decrease the emission of CO_2 in the atmosphere, photocatalytic reduction of CO_2 is a suitable approach. For environmental CO_2 reduction, the photocatalytic activity of nanomaterials such as BiVO_4 and doped nanomaterials under visible and ultraviolet (UV) radiation shows environmentally friendly results, which is also part of the current review. Also, the energy-intensive process for producing ammonia and other nitrogen-based compounds must switch from the current fossil fuel-based industrial process to a cleaner and green route. Considering this, N_2 fixation using the photocatalysis process is an emerging area of research. The review also briefly discusses the recent progress in photocatalytic N_2 fixation using BiVO_4 -based composites. Thus, this review systematically highlights the importance of BiVO_4 for water splitting and water remediation, considering the structural, electronic, and optical properties on one hand while outlining and discussing strategies to improve the performance of BiVO_4 and its composites for scalable technologies.

2 Properties of BiVO_4

2.1 Structural properties

The photocatalytic performance of BiVO_4 highly depends on its crystalline structure. The different possible arrangements of atoms in the crystal structure dictate the photocatalytic activities and lead to the formation of different energy bandgaps. Distortion in crystal structure results in the non-coinciding of positive and negative charges, which promotes the lone pair effect and enhances the internal electric field. This favors the effective separation of photo-generated electron-hole pairs and improves the photocatalytic response of the material. A deeper understanding can be anticipated amongst three different crystal structures for BiVO_4 [44]. Pucherite mineral is one of the three types of crystal structure. It is a mineral that occurs naturally and displays an orthorhombic structure. The second type of crystal structure of BiVO_4 is the scheelite structure (Fig. 3(a)). It can be easily transformed either into monoclinic clinobisvanite or tetragonal dreyerite structure [45]. In both these phases, each bismuth atom is covered by a total of eight oxygen atoms. These oxygen atoms are part of VO_4 units. It leads to the formation of a dodecahedron. Also, all the V atoms are synchronized with four oxygen atoms, leading to a

Figure 3 Various crystal structures of BiVO_4 , (a) tetragonal scheelite, (b) monoclinic scheelite, (c) tetragonal zircon [47, 48]. Data retrieved from the Materials Project for BiVO_4 from database version v2021.11.10 (CC BY 4.0).

tetrahedron formation. In the monoclinic phase, the surroundings of both the bismuth and vanadium atoms are distorted to a greater extent when compared to the tetragonal phase. This affects the four-fold symmetry in the tetragonal phase (Fig. 3(b)), whereas the deformation is much more in the monoclinic phase. The third type of crystal structure of BiVO_4 is the zircon-type structure. It consists of a tetragonal lattice where all the bismuth atoms are covered by six VO_4 units. The alignment of this structure is shown in Fig. 3(c). Thus, the symmetric polyhedron crystal nature of pucherite and dreyerite polymorphs is detrimental to its photocatalytic activity. In contrast, the distorted nature of the monoclinic scheelite structure is very advantageous for improved photocatalytic activity [46].

The monoclinic scheelite BiVO_4 has been investigated for the finest photocatalytic efficiency among these crystalline structures. The BiVO_4 monoclinic crystal phase has a space group of $I2/a$. The structure shows significant distortion due to the local environment of the Bi and V ions, leading to several distinct bond lengths. In the monoclinic structure, each Bi atom is coordinated by eight oxygen atoms. These oxygen atoms are distributed unevenly, resulting in four different Bi–O bond lengths: 2.35, 2.37, 2.52, and 2.63 Å [38, 49, 50]. The vanadium atoms in the monoclinic BiVO_4 are coordinated by four oxygen atoms, forming a tetrahedral arrangement. However, due to distortion in the local environment, there are two different V–O bond lengths: 1.69 and 1.76 Å. The monoclinic structure shows a significant distortion that leads to the loss of four-fold symmetry. The different bond lengths indicate the local environment around the Bi and V atoms is not uniform, which can influence the electronic structure and properties of the material. The reduced symmetry also impacts the light absorption and charge transport properties, making this phase more active in specific applications like photocatalysis. Also, along the crystallographic axis, it has an alternate arrangement of bismuth and vanadium atoms resembling a layered structure. Kudo et al. [5] disclosed that the monoclinic phase has a higher photocatalytic efficiency prominently because of the relatively small energy bandgap (2.4 eV), which lies in the visible region, while zircon-type (2.9 eV) only reacts to the ultraviolet light absorption [31]. Compared to other structures, the local surroundings of Bi and V are significantly disordered for the monoclinic scheelite phase. This improves photogenerated electron-hole pairs' photocatalytic capability and dispersion due to the deformation-induced internal electric field and polarization effect [45].

The tetragonal phase of BiVO_4 is less common and can be found at higher temperatures or under specific synthesis conditions [51]. It belongs to the tetragonal crystal system with a space group of $I41/a$. In the tetragonal structure, each Bi atom is also coordinated

by eight oxygen atoms. However, the arrangement is more symmetric, with two different Bi–O bond lengths: 2.4 and 2.47 Å. This indicates a more uniform local environment around the Bi atoms than the monoclinic structure [38, 50]. The vanadium atoms in the tetragonal BiVO₄ are also coordinated by four oxygen atoms in a tetrahedral arrangement. In contrast to the monoclinic phase, all V–O bond lengths are equal at 1.73 Å, reflecting a more symmetric and less distorted environment. Thus, the tetragonal structure has higher symmetry than the monoclinic phase, leading to uniform bond lengths and a more regular arrangement of atoms [52].

Experimental investigations have highlighted the influence of crystal structures on the PC performance of BiVO₄. Saimi Tokunaga et al. studied monoclinic and tetragonal BiVO₄ for photocatalytic O₂ evolution. They found that the monoclinic phase exhibited significantly higher activity under visible light ($\lambda > 420$ nm) and UV light ($300 < \lambda < 380$ nm), attributed to the lone pair effect and polyhedral distortion enhancing charge separation [31]. Similarly, Tulsi Dabodiya and co-workers compared the PC performance of monoclinic and mixed-phase BiVO₄ for Rhodamine B degradation. The monoclinic phase achieved a higher degradation efficiency (95%) and faster kinetics ($K_{\text{avg}} = 0.0718 \text{ min}^{-1}$) compared to the mixed phase (87%; $K_{\text{avg}} = 0.0436 \text{ min}^{-1}$) [53]. Xi Zhang et al. synthesized monoclinic and tetragonal BiVO₄ to study their optical properties and PC activity for methylene blue (MB) degradation. The monoclinic phase, with a smaller bandgap (2.34 eV vs. 3.11 eV for tetragonal), demonstrated superior visible light absorption and photocatalytic activity due to improved charge separation and reduced recombination losses. In contrast, the tetragonal phase showed negligible activity [54]. These studies emphasize the critical role of phase selection in optimizing photocatalysts for enhanced performance.

Thus, the theoretical and experimental investigations discussed above are synonymous, and greater studies are required to understand the behavior of the different polymorphs in photocatalysis.

2.2 Role of energy band

The electronic band configuration, which includes the bandgap and the position of band edges, plays a pivotal role in defining materials' optical, electrical, and photocatalytic behavior [55].

2.2.1 Electronic properties

The property of a semiconductor is highly dependent on the position of the conduction band (CB) and valence band (VB), i.e., bandgap. To make it responsive in visible light, the bandgap energy should be decreased via enhancement of the VB edge. With the introduction of cations, the electrons inhabit low-energy *s* orbitals, and consequently, the VB edge can be increased [30]. This requirement is fulfilled by Bi present in BiVO₄ packed with 6s orbitals because hybridization of bismuth 6s and oxygen 2p enhances the VB edge and thus reduces the bandgap energy. Walsh et al. estimated the direct bandgap of BiVO₄ to be 2.16 eV by utilizing density functional theory (DFT) for monoclinic BiVO₄ [56]. Its VB comprises O 2p and a minor component of Bi 6p and V 3d, whilst CB is composed principally of V 3d associated with Bi 6p and O 2p orbitals. These conclusions are corroborated experimentally by Payne et al. [57]. However, slightly different band structures of BiVO₄ were proposed by Zhao et al. [45]. From DFT

calculations, it can be inferred that VB consists of non-bonding O 2p states while CB consists of V 3d states that are weakly bonded. The minimum estimated indirect energy band gap is 2.17 eV, whereas other direct bandgap energy is slightly bigger. Both the groups provided us with the results of DFT computations, and it was compared to other metal oxide semiconductors; the effective masses (m_{eff}) of carriers are much smaller in BiVO₄. Approximately, the m_{eff} for photogenerated holes and electrons was 0.3 m_0 , as calculated by Payne et al. [57]. On the other hand, the Zhao group indicated that the m_{eff} for photogenerated holes at the top of VB is 0.7 m_0 , while for electrons present at the bottom of CB is 0.9 m_0 [45]. When compared to other semiconductors such as TiO₂ or In₂O₃, the photo-generated carriers whose m_{eff} are lower are advantageous for photocatalytic activity because: (i) The charge carriers can easily be separated and transported, (ii) the lifetime of photoexcited species is extended, and (iii) recombination rates are diminished.

2.2.2 Optical properties

Zhao et al. [45] inferred very substantial optical anisotropy around absorption edges inside the monoclinic phase of BiVO₄ from the DFT algorithmic results, owing to the aforementioned peculiar electronic configuration and damaged crystal structure. The lower limit of absorption of wavelengths by photons with their electric field (*E*) polarized along the *a* and *c* axes seems to be 100 nm bigger than it was along the *b*-axis, as illustrated by the refractive indexes and various absorption coefficients along varied lattice axes in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b). The maximum absorbance at 330 nm is primarily induced by photons polarized along the *b*-axis; meanwhile, the maximum at 440 nm is caused mainly by photons polarized along the *a* and *c* axes. The V–O and Bi–O bonding dipoles were reported to vary along the *b*-axis; however, they were identical along the *a* and *c* axes. Hence, electron transfer between upper VB to lower CB is prohibited for polarization across the *b* axis; however, *E* was permitted across both the *a* and *c* orientations. Thus, the unique optical characteristics along the *b* plane, relative to both the *a* and *c* directions, could be utilized to enhance the photocatalytic activity of BiVO₄ by exposing more significant portions of the (100) and (001) crystalline facets [11, 31, 58, 59].

2.3 Role of morphology on the photocatalytic activity

Different morphological structures of BiVO₄ produced by various processes substantially impact its photocatalytic activity. Safia Lofti et al. have critically examined the influence of morphology on the photocatalytic degradation of BiVO₄ photocatalysts. Their findings indicate that BiVO₄ materials with porous and hierarchical morphologies consistently exhibit superior photocatalytic performance. This enhancement is primarily attributed to the significantly increased effective surface area, which promotes more efficient mass transport and facilitates the diffusion of pollutant molecules within the porous and hierarchical structures. These features provide a greater significant number of accessible active sites, thereby enhancing the rate of photocatalytic degradation through improved adsorption, charge separation, and reaction kinetics [61]. In a separate investigation, Rayees Rather and co-workers systematically evaluated the effect of BiVO₄ morphology on PEC water oxidation. Their study analyses the role of elongated and anisotropic morphologies in modulating the catalytic efficiency of the water oxidation reaction. The directional growth of BiVO₄ crystals along a specific axis facilitates the exposure of high-index

Figure 4 (a) The absorption coefficient and (b) the refractive index of monoclinic clinobisvanite BiVO₄ for different polarization vectors as a function of photon energy. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [45], © the Owner Societies 2011. SEM images of (c) BiVO₄ (BVO) composite, (d) Nickel ferrite (NFO), (e) BVO/NFO composite, and (f) BVO/Ag/NFO composites. (g) Hydrogen production rates and (h) PL spectra of BVO, NFO, BVO/NFO, and BVO/Ag/NFO, respectively. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [60], © Elsevier Ltd and Techna Group S.r.l. 2022.

facets, which are thermodynamically advantageous for water oxidation. Developing anisotropic shapes, such as polyhedra, decahedra, and pyramids, enhances the exposure of these energetically favorable facets, thereby significantly improving the catalytic performance. Moreover, anisotropic morphologies increase the effective surface area, amplifying both the adsorption capacity for reactants and the density of active sites on the exposed facets, thereby promoting more efficient electron transfer and enhancing overall reaction kinetics [62].

A separate study demonstrated that tailoring the morphology of photocatalysts can substantially improve their performance. Notably, three-dimensional architectures exhibit enhanced photocatalytic efficiency, attributed to their higher density of reactive sites, expanded surface area, and efficient molecular

diffusion of pollutants. Strategic modification of synthesis protocols and reaction parameters enables the design of optimized morphologies. Furthermore, photocatalysis governed by facet orientation shows significant potential; however, a lack of extensive experimental validation and theoretical insights presents a considerable limitation in this field [63]. Nanotube and porous morphologies have demonstrated superior photocatalytic performance due to their distinct structural advantages. Their larger surface area enhances light absorption and increases the availability of active sites for photocatalytic processes. Nanotubes offer improved charge carrier separation and reduced recombination, while porous structures facilitate efficient mass transfer of reactants and products. These properties can be optimized through the controlled use of surfactants and additives during synthesis,

enhancing photocatalyst-reactant interactions and overall photocatalytic efficiency, making them ideal for energy and environmental applications [38]. Additionally, microboat and microsphere-like morphologies have also shown enhanced photocatalytic activity [64]. Xue Meng and colleagues studied various BiVO_4 morphologies synthesized using co-polymer-assisted and hydrothermal methods, including polyhedral, rod-like, tubular, leaf-like, and spherical structures. Among these, rod-like morphologies exhibited a significantly higher surface area, which increased active sites for reactant adsorption and light interaction, thereby promoting efficient photocatalytic reactions. Furthermore, the rod-like structure improved charge separation and transfer, minimizing electron-hole recombination, making it a promising candidate for advanced photocatalytic applications [65].

Based on the above information, morphology-dependent studies indicate that no single morphology universally outperforms others; instead, the optimal choice depends on the specific application. However, a high surface area remains a key factor in all cases, as it ensures greater exposure of catalytic reaction sites.

3 Applications of BiVO_4

3.1 Hydrogen production through photocatalytic water splitting

Water splitting is a simple process in which hydrogen and oxygen are separated from water molecules. It is an efficient, environment-friendly, and economical process of breaking down water that could underpin the hydrogen economy. Here, energy is absorbed by the material and converted into chemical energy through a complex pathway. Water splitting occurs as follows

The top level of the VB should have a value greater than the redox potential of $\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, while the bottom level of the CB should be more negative than the redox potential of H^+/H_2 . Hence, considering this, in general, for the light of wavelength 1100 nm, the theoretical minimum bandgap for water splitting is 1.23 eV [66].

There are various techniques for water splitting, such as PEC [67], thermal decomposition [68], photocatalytic [66], radiolysis [69], photobiological [70], electrolysis [71], etc. A comparative study of different processes based on cost-effective analysis has been reviewed by Wang et al. [72]. Among these, photocatalytic water splitting is an ideal, low-cost process with energy efficiency, a simple setup, and high hydrogen production potential, occurring on semiconductor nanomaterials under solar energy. For commercial adoption, the process requires the development and design of visible-light-active materials for photocatalysis and photoelectrodes, which are crucial for the efficient conversion of sunlight into chemical energy. Nanomaterials have extremely small feature sizes and large surface areas, while approaches like band structural modification, quantum dot sensitization, etc., make them beneficial materials for photoelectrodes [44]. A photoelectrode for water-splitting should have effective characteristics such as: (i) It should absorb and harvest maximum wavelengths of light and initialize electrochemical (EC) transformation. (ii) It should be relatively stable under harsh PEC conditions. (iii) The electrode should have the ability to catalyze both hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER) at low overpotentials as well as the rapid movement of charge carriers [73, 74].

OER and HER are multi-electron electrochemical reactions having slow kinetics, huge over-potentials, and multi-step reactions [75]. OER is a limiting reaction process producing molecular oxygen through chemical reactions, such as electrolysis of water into hydrogen and oxygen, oxygenic photosynthesis followed by water oxidation, and electrocatalytic oxygen evolution from oxides and oxoacids. OER follows four-electron transport processes, and it is considered the bottleneck step of the whole water-splitting process because it has sluggish kinetics due to the involvement of many photons/electrons, especially in alkaline conditions. Hence, a catalyst is needed to accelerate the process by decreasing the electrochemical potential [76]. In the PEC water-splitting process, the main intermediates observed in the OER are oxygen (O_2^-), hydroxyl (HO^-), and hydroperoxyl (HOO^-) [77]. Currently, for reducing energy consumption and enhancing energy conversion efficiency, the OER process is widely explored using precious metals and their oxides such as Ir, Ru, IrO_2 , RuO_2 , etc. Hence, it is a challenge to find an alternative and reduce the overall cost of scalable applications [78].

To do so, the exploration of effective catalysts having lower cost and high performance for the overall water splitting process, include: i) transition metals like sulfides, nitrides, carbides, and phosphides are representative catalysts in both acid and alkaline solutions for HER, and ii) active noble metal-free catalysts such as layered double hydroxide (LDH), ferric oxyhydroxide (FeOOH), vanadate, etc. for OER are being developed [79]. Active catalysts for OER and HER can make processes more energy-efficient and decrease the dynamic overpotential [80]. However, we cannot use different materials every time in electrodes because it may create inconvenience in the assembly of cells and catalyst design. To overcome this, in recent developments, bifunctional electrocatalysts, which can catalyze both HER and OER in an alkaline solution, have been discovered. These catalysts include NiCo_2O_4 hollow micro cuboid [81], MoO_2 nanosheets [82], hollow Co_3O_4 [83], MnO/CN superlattices [84], FeMnP films, Co-P film [85], $\text{Ni}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{P}$ microstructures [80], Co-Mn carbonate hydroxide [86], etc. A single particulate photocatalyst with one-step excitation or a coupled system of two individual particulate photocatalysts with two-step excitation via electron transfer mediator exists. The second approach mostly requires metals and semiconductor material and is called co-catalysts. Photocatalytic water splitting materials can be divided into two categories: (i) metal oxide and oxy-nitrides with metal particles on top, and (ii) metal-free catalysts [87]. An extended approach is the PEC water-splitting process in which water molecules in the presence of sunlight are dissociated into their components, i.e., O_2 and H_2 , by a suitable photocatalyst with an applied external potential [88].

We can also classify water-splitting systems using organic-inorganic composites such as (a) dye-sensitized photocatalysts for hydrogen production and (b) Z-scheme-type photocatalysts for hydrogen and oxygen production (see Figs. 5(a) and 5(b)) [89].

(a) Dye-sensitized photocatalysts for hydrogen production: This type of water splitting is a replacement source for existing technologies where the production of hydrogen is achieved under visible light irradiation. Here, dye molecules are used as light absorbers, which absorb visible light and transfer the photo-excited electrons to inorganic semiconductors and produce hydrogen using these electrons [90, 91]. Due to its ability to separate charges from the inorganic semiconductor, charge separation is easier for a dye than with a photocatalyst. The basic mechanism of dye-sensitized

Figure 5 Two types of the water-splitting systems using organic-inorganic composites. (a) Dye-sensitized photocatalysts for hydrogen production and (b) Z-scheme-type photocatalysts for hydrogen and oxygen production. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [89], © Watanabe, M. et al. 2017.

solar cells is as follows: First, by photoexcitation, dye reaches an excited state, and injects the electrons from the excited state of the oxidation potential of dye to the inorganic semiconductor's conduction band within several hundred femtoseconds timespan. The injected electrons move toward the inorganic semiconductor surface (or to the catalyst) and react with the proton to form hydrogen [92].

(b) Z-scheme-type photocatalysts for hydrogen and oxygen production: This water-splitting system contains photocatalysts for H_2 and O_2 evolution and an electron mediator. The mediator separates the charges between two semiconductors, which increases the efficiency of water splitting. Firstly, an electron is passed on to the H_2 generation photocatalyst via a mediator, and then, by light absorption, the second charge separation process happens [93]. Here, during photo-excitation, the previously excited electrons can regain their high energy, which results in hydrogen production by transferred electrons and oxygen production by holes [89]. The n-type semiconductors developed for utilizing this mechanism are TiO_2 , WO_3 , and $BiVO_4$. All these can also be used for O_2 production during oxidation reactions. The p-type semiconductors used are $TaON$, TiO_2 , ZrO_2 , etc. for H_2 generation through reduction reaction [94].

3.1.1 Nano- $BiVO_4$ for photocatalytic hydrogen production

An ideal photocatalytic hydrogen production catalyst requires a

suitable band edge for water oxidation, visible light absorption, and a lower electron-hole recombination rate. Table 1 shows photocatalytic hydrogen generation using $BiVO_4$ -based composites under a visible light source. To achieve efficient overall water splitting, the potential of the VB must be more positive than the oxidation potential of H_2O to O_2 (1.23 V vs. NHE), while the CB must be more negative than the reduction potential of H^+ to H_2 (0 V vs. NHE at pH 0) [95]. In the case of $BiVO_4$, the CB potential is relatively positive compared to the reduction potential of H^+ to H_2 , which makes the photocatalytic HER challenging for bare $BiVO_4$ [96]. This mismatch in band alignment restricts the material's ability to efficiently drive hydrogen production through photocatalysis [97].

Different strategies and material combination techniques are used to improve its performance. Amongst them, the Z-scheme approach is majorly used, wherein n-type $BiVO_4$ is combined with a p-type material in the presence or absence of an electron mediator. Besides the material costs, the charge transfer mediator should be selected to not cause a shielding effect, or lower the performance. Therefore, choosing the right p-type material and electron mediator is imperative for a high-performance composite. To do so, different research groups have designed different composites with $BiVO_4$ in a Z-scheme style to improve the performance of the device [98–104].

T. Nawaz et al. demonstrated a composite of n-type $BiVO_4$ with

Table 1 Photocatalytic hydrogen generation using $BiVO_4$ -based composites

Sr. No.	Material	Method	Light source	Reactant solution/sacrificial agents/co-catalyst	Catalyst loading (mg)	Activity	Ref.
1.	$BiVO_4$	WC	Visible light ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	400 mL (0.04 M Na_2SO_3 and 0.1 M Na_2S)	50	$10.6 \mu mol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[105]
	$Bi_2O_3/BiVO_4$	HT	Visible light ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	400 mL (0.04 M Na_2SO_3 and 0.1 M Na_2S)	50	$171.13 \mu mol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	
2.	$BiVO_4/ZnCdS$	HT	300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	100 mL (0.25 M Na_2S and 0.35 M Na_2SO_3)	10	$152.5 \mu mol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[106]
3.	$ZnIn_2S_4/NiO/BiVO_4$	RME, WI, CC	350 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	200 mL (1 M formaldehyde)/1 wt.% Pt	300	$9082.97 \mu mol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[107]
4.	$AC/BiVO_4$	HT	Visible light	60 mL DW	1	$510 \mu mol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[108]
5.	$CdS/BiVO_4$	HT	300 W Xe lamp	100 mL (1M Na_2SO_3)	50	$197.2 mmol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[109]
6.	$BiVO_4/TiO_2$	SG, SCH	300 W Xe lamp	120 mL (methanol)	100	$14300 \mu mol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[110]
7.	$BiVO_4/rGO$	HT	200 W Hg-Xe arc lamp	50 mL (DW + 0.5 ml ethanol)	5	$11.5 \mu mol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[111]
8.	$ZnIn_2S_4/BiVO_4$	HT	300 W Xe lamp	100 mL (DW and TEOA, volume ratio 9:1)/3 wt.% Pt	10	$5.944 mmol \cdot g^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$	[112]
9.	$g-C_3N_4/BiVO_4$	HT, SI	Xe lamp	80 mL DW + 20 mL of methanol/Pt	50	$53.25 \mu mol \cdot h^{-1}$	[113]

(Continued)

Sr. No.	Material	Method	Light source	Reactant solution/sacrificial agents/co-catalyst	Catalyst loading (mg)	Activity	Ref.
10.	ZnIn ₂ S ₄ /rGO/BiVO ₄	HT	350 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	200 mL DW with 0.2 M formaldehyde/ 1 wt.% Pt	300	563.3 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[114]
11.	WO ₃ /g-C ₃ N ₄ /BiVO ₄	HT	500 W metal halide lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	200 mL (0.04 M Na ₂ SO ₃ and 0.1 M Na ₂ S)	50	432 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[115]
12.	BiVO ₄ /TiO ₂	ES, ALD	300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	40 mL (DW and methanol in ratio 3:1)	50	6 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[116]
13.	g-C ₃ N ₄ /Au/BiVO ₄	HT	300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	20 mL TEOA and 80 mL DW	50	410 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[117]
	g-C ₃ N ₄ /BiVO ₄	HT	300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	20 mL TEOA and 80 mL DW	50	23.3 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	
14.	g-C ₃ N ₄ /Pt/BiVO ₄	TD, HT	300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	100 mL Na ₂ SO ₃ solution (0.05 M)	100	7.2 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[118]
15.	Ag/LaVO ₄ /BiVO ₄	SCO, PD, PP	400 W metal halide lamp	150 mL 0.5 M Na ₂ S + 0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₃	15	55.8 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[119]
	LaVO ₄ /BiVO ₄	SCO, PP	400 W metal halide lamp	150 mL 0.5 M Na ₂ S + 0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₃	15	45.5 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	
16.	ZnIn ₂ S ₄ /RGO/BiVO ₄	HT, WI, LR	350 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	200 mL DW/Pt	200	4.1 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[99]
17.	CdS/BiVO ₄	HT, EI	300 W Xe ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	50 mL aq. sol ⁿ with 25% methanol/Pt	10	0.57 mmol·h ⁻¹	[104]
18.	Ag/BiVO ₄	HT	300 W Xe lamp	ethanol-triethylamine aq. sol ⁿ	50	205 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[120]
19.	BiVO ₄ -Ru/SrTiO ₃ :Rh	WI	300 W Xe lamp	150 mL DW	200	47.2 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[121]
20.	g-C ₃ N ₄ /Pt/BiVO ₄	TD, HT, PD	300 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	100 mL (0.05 M Na ₂ SO ₃ solution)	100	7.2 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[122]
	BiVO ₄ /Ag/NiFe ₂ O ₄	HT	1000 W Xe lamp	100 mL DW (0.2 M Na ₂ S and 0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₃)	500	452 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	
21.	BiVO ₄ /Ag/NiFe ₂ O ₄	HT	1000 W Xe lamp	100 mL DW (0.2 M Na ₂ S and 0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₃)	500	326 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[60]
	BiVO ₄	HT	1000 W Xe lamp	100 mL DW (0.2 M Na ₂ S and 0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₃)	500	105 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	
22.	BiVO ₄ NPs	WC, ES	LED lamp (50 W), $\lambda = 450$ nm	10 mL methanol + 90 mL DW/Pt	100	1.66 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[123]
23.	BiVO ₄ /InVO ₄ /CdS	SIL	350 W Xe lamp ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	150 mL wastewater	100	4188 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[124]
24.	Pt-BiVO ₄ /TiO ₂	SG, PD	150 W Xe arc lamp	150 mL aq. sol. of ethanol (0.05 mol·h ⁻¹)/ 0.5 wt.% Pt	15	32.2 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[100]
25.	BiVO ₄ /ZnIn ₂ S ₄	HT	Visible light ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	8 mL TEOA and 72 mL ultrapure water	50	2242 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[125]
26.	gC ₃ N ₄ /Au/BiVO ₄	HT	Visible light ($\lambda > 420$ nm)	90 mL DW + 10 mL TEOA + methanol	50	2986 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[126]
27.	Cu /BiVO ₄	DC	500 W Xe lamp	50 mL methanol	Film	132 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[127]
28.	Pt-BiVO ₄	PP	LED; 300 W	150 mL aq. sol ⁿ of 25% ethanol	15	115.7 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[128]
29.	Fe ₃ N/BiVO ₄	EI	300 W Xe lamp	80 mL of lactic acid aq. solution	50	1420.7 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[129]
30.	g-C ₃ N ₄ /BiVO ₄	TP, HT	300 W Xe lamp	100 mL of TEOA (v/v TEOA:H ₂ O = 1:9)	20	80.7 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	[130]

p-type NiFe₂O₄ (NFO, a spinel ferrite) mediated by Ag nanoparticles (NPs) prepared via HT. NFO shows a bandgap of 1.7 eV and has appropriate band positioning relative to BiVO₄ for the Z-scheme. BiVO₄ displays a non-magnetic nature, whereas NFO is magnetic, which becomes beneficial for commercial magnetic separation of composite powder from the solution after use. Ag NPs are size-tunable and have a localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) effect. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of these photocatalysts are shown in Figs. 4(c)–4(f). Pure NFO shows agglomerated circular-shaped NPs, and pure BiVO₄ has rod/wire-shaped structures, while their composite BiVO₄/NFO

are rod-shaped NPs. Thus, the conversion of irregular-shaped nanowires into nanorods takes place with the addition of NFO into BiVO₄. Further, in BiVO₄/Ag/NFO composite, complete transformation into nanorods has distinct smooth morphology. The overall composite BiVO₄/Ag/NiFe₂O₄ in an electrolyte consisting of deionized (DI) water and sacrificial agents Na₂S and Na₂SO₃ showed production of H₂ at the rate of 452 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, which was four-fold improvement than bare BiVO₄ (105 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) as shown in Fig. 4(g). Additionally, photoluminescence (PL) spectra of all the samples are shown in Fig. 4(h). Lower values of PL signify that the material has a lower recombination rate and

higher photocatalytic property is expected. The decreasing order of the PL intensity is $\text{BiVO}_4 > \text{NFO} > \text{BiVO}_4/\text{NFO} > \text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}/\text{NFO}$ [60]. Other Z-scheme composites like $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{ZnCdS}$ by M. Imran et al. showed a tenfold improvement in H_2 production rate ($152.5 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) than ZnCdS . Also, the successful integration of ZnCdS NPs onto BiVO_4 nanorods took place. Here, photocurrent responses and electron impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies were carried out on the different samples as shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b). It was observed that the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{ZnCdS}$ composite demonstrated much higher photocurrent than the bare samples indicating a lower rate of electron-hole recombination, and higher charge separation efficiency. From the EIS studies, $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{ZnCdS}$ heterostructure displayed a smaller arc radius on the Nyquist plot, while lower frequency shift in Bode plots compared to other samples shows that the reduced recombination rates of electron-hole pair improved the photocatalytic rate of H_2 production. SEM images for different samples are shown in Figs. 6(c)–6(f). The morphology of BiVO_4 and ZnCdS are rod-shaped and irregular-shaped NPs, respectively. Meanwhile, for the composite, the ZnCdS NPs were successfully loaded on BiVO_4 nanorods (Figs. 6(e) and 6(f)). This heterostructure formation is the primary reason for improved performance. A possible explanation is shown in the schematic diagram (Fig. 6(g)). The CB of BiVO_4 lies above the VB of ZnCdS but is lower than the value required for H_2 evolution. As a result, no H_2 production occurs for bare BiVO_4 ; however, a Z-scheme electron transfer pathway is observed in the composite, which facilitates H_2 production [106].

In another work, Y. Fan and researchers designed a CdS decorated $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{InVO}_4$ Z-scheme, which, in the presence of Pt co-catalyst, delivered a hydrogen production rate of $4188 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$

in model wastewater. Pt is one of the most used co-catalysts in hydrogen production applications because it shows the SPR effect and favors the H_2 evolution at the lowest overpotential. Even though BiVO_4 , InVO_4 , and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{InVO}_4$ did not show considerable H_2 production activity, the decoration with CdS significantly improved their performance [124]. The CdS was used in combination with BiVO_4 by Lin and co-workers for a direct Z-scheme approach, but in this case, no co-catalysts were used. Figures 7(a) and 7(b) display the SEM images of the samples. Here, hollow cubic structures are observed for BiVO_4 (Fig. 7(a)), while the CdSe flower-shaped NPs are successfully grown on the surface of BiVO_4 (Fig. 7(b)). The ultraviolet–visible diffuse reflectance spectrum (UV–DRS) helps to evaluate the bandgap of the material which can be derived from the Tauc plots. In this case, the obtained bandgap values of pure BiVO_4 and CdS are 2.40 and 2.27 eV, respectively which further decreases to 2.24 eV for the optimized (CdS/ BiVO_4). The reduction in bandgap signifies enhanced absorption of the visible light spectrum by the material, a characteristic ideally required for an efficient photocatalyst. The images in Figs. 7(c) and 7(d) support this argument as greater H_2 production, lower impedance value, and higher photocurrent are observed by the optimized composite (CdS/BiVO_4), which is many times higher than the bare samples. A very high H_2 evolution performance is delivered by the CdS/BiVO_4 i.e., $190.1 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and excellent recyclability for 6 cycles was observed [109].

Strategies like heterojunction of n-n type like $\text{Ta}_2\text{O}_5/\text{BiVO}_4$ [131] or p-n type like $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ [105] have also been explored for n-type BiVO_4 . F. Shafiq and co-workers significantly improved the performance of the pure BiVO_4 sample by 16 times to get a $171.3 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ hydrogen production rate. To achieve this, they

Figure 6 (a) Photocurrent response vs. time for BiVO_4 , ZnCdS , and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{ZnCdS}$ heterostructure ($\lambda \geq 420 \text{ nm}$). (b) Corresponding EIS curves. (c) SEM image for as-prepared BiVO_4 nanorods. (d) SEM image of ZnCdS nanoparticles. (e) SEM image of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{ZnCdS}$ sample at low resolution. (f) SEM image of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{ZnCdS}$ sample at high resolution. (g) A schematic diagram illustrating the band positions and charge transfer process for $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{ZnCdS}$ heterostructure. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [106], © Hydrogen Energy Publications LLC, 2022.

Figure 7 Morphology of (a) BiVO₄ and (b) CdS/BiVO₄-25 observed by SEM. (c) The hydrogen generation rate of CdS and CdS/BiVO₄. (d) The photocurrent–time curves of photocatalyst under UV–vis light illumination. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [109], © Elsevier Ltd. 2020.

combined p-type Bi₂O₃ with BiVO₄ to form a p-n heterojunction composite [105]. Theoretical studies by J. Pan et al. analyzed the role of oxygen-defect engineering in improving the activity of {110} facets using computational DFT modeling by the VASP software package. Figures 8(a) and 8(c) reveal the total and partial density of states (DOS) for BiVO₄ with and without oxygen vacancies (O_{vac}). It is seen that the energy bandgap decreases for BiVO₄ with O_{vac}. Also, Figs. 8(b) and 8(d) show the average electrostatic potentials along the z-axis for both cases and the corresponding energy band diagrams. The oxygen defect engineering is crucial because: (i) optical absorption improves due to greater electronic transitions simulated by O_{vac}-induced local electronic states, (ii) it helps to induce the internal electric field needed for effective electron-hole separation, and (iii) mismatched electrons and dangling bonds, stimulate the activity of surrounding atoms [132]. Other factors like controlling particle size, the influence of calcination temperature during the material synthesis [123], facet engineering [62], and morphology tailoring [133] affecting the production of hydrogen have also been studied.

3.1.2 PEC water splitting

PEC water splitting is a solar energy-based technology that, despite its complexity, is environmentally safe and has the potential to drive hydrogen technology toward zero emissions [134]. The principle of PEC water splitting is based on the conversion of light energy into electricity in the presence of a light-responsive semiconductor having a suitable bandgap and an aqueous electrolyte [135].

The performance and properties of photoelectrode can be measured using photocurrent density. The measurement of photocurrent density can be achieved by two main components: a

potentiostat and a light source. Based on the type of light source used, there are two main experimental configurations: one for measuring performance under high-intensity white light and the other for measuring wavelength-dependent properties using low-intensity light [73]. In the PEC water-splitting process, catalysts decrease the required cell potential to drive water splitting [136]. They also transfer photoexcited holes into the electrolyte in the water-splitting process. One of the best known heterogeneous catalysts is based on platinum for hydrogen evolution reaction.

Other materials like nickel, alloys of nickel, cobalt, and molybdenum are promising candidates for hydrogen production. Similarly, metal phosphides (e.g., Ni₃P) and metal nitrides (e.g., TiN) are also used as electrocatalysts. Other groups of elements, like oxides of cobalt or nickel and sulfides of molybdenum, are also used as photo-electrocatalysts in HER [137]. Similarly, active metals such as cobalt, nickel, iron, and metal oxy-hydrides (e.g., NiOOH) can be used as a catalyst with a photoactive substrate like BiVO₄ in PEC water-splitting [138, 139]. The practical use of BiVO₄ for PEC water splitting is mainly limited due to its poor charge separation ability. Also, the standard benchmark value of solar-to-hydrogen (STH) efficiency of 10% is still a distant dream. Hence, substantial efforts are needed to maximize the photocurrent density response for higher hydrogen production [36].

BiVO₄ is an n-type semiconductor that acts as a photoanode in a standard PEC cell. The cathode is Pt-based, and an aqueous electrolyte separates the two electrodes. The PEC water splitting consists of several essential steps: light absorption, charge generation, charge separation, and subsequent charge transfer at the electrode–electrolyte interface. When the BiVO₄ photoanode is immersed in the electrolytic solution, a difference in energy levels at

Figure 8 The total and partial DOS of BiVO₄ {110} facets (a) without the O_{vac} and (c) with the O_{vac}. (b) The average electrostatic potentials along the z-axis and (d) the band edge positions of BiVO₄ {010} facets relative to the water redox potential with (pink) and without (black) the O_{vac}. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [132], © Pan, J. et al. 2022.

the interface is created. To maintain the electrostatic balance, there is a transfer of charge carriers between the electrodes and the interface of the electrolyte till the equilibrium is established. During this stage, the electrolytic redox potential (E_{redox}) and the photoanode's Fermi energy level (E_{fn}) coincide, resulting in the upward bending of the CB and VB of the photoanode. Hence, in the absence of illumination, two layers are formed at the electrode/electrolyte interface, namely, Helmholtz and Gouy-Chapman layers. Once the PEC cell is illuminated, photo holes and photoelectrons are generated at the photoanode's valence band and conduction band, respectively. The interfacial band bending results in the migration of generated holes towards the electrolyte while electrons move through BiVO₄ to FTO along the external circuit in the presence of applied bias [50]. Thus, two half-reactions happen in PEC water splitting: water oxidation to O₂ at the photoanode and water reduction to H₂ at the counter electrode.

Oxidation at photoanode (OER):

Reduction at the counter electrode (HER):

The efficiency of PEC water splitting can be calculated as

$$\eta = (1.229 \text{ V} - V_{\text{bias}}) I_p / P \quad (4)$$

where, 1.229 V is standard potential required to form H₂ and O₂ from H₂O, V_{bias} is applied bias voltage (Volt), I_p is measured photocurrent density (A·m⁻²), P is incident light intensity (W·m⁻²) [140].

The BiVO₄ faces a significant challenge related to higher charge recombination and photo corrosion, limiting its overall water oxidation kinetics. In solving the issue, a widely used heterojunction technique has been tried to improve the water-splitting performance. The choice of material for heterojunction becomes critical while deciding the final device structure. Some things to be considered while selecting the material include: i) uniformity in the heterojunction formation and ii) proper band alignments of the materials. Table 2 highlights the comparative performances of BiVO₄-based photoanodes for PEC water splitting. Some of the prominent works are explained below.

Ma and co-workers investigated a BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O p-n heterojunction using a simple HT, chemical bath deposition (CBD), and electrodeposition (ED) method. Figures 9(a)–9(c) present the SEM images of the various samples, revealing that BiVO₄ exhibits a compact nanosheet structure with loosely distributed Ag NPs on its surface. The final composite BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O shows compact cubic nanocubes wherein Cu₂O wraps BiVO₄/Ag photoelectrode. The built-in potential developed at the interface of the p-n junction (where Cu₂O acts as p-type and BiVO₄ is n-type) and the SPR effect of Ag NPs improved the PEC properties. The ternary composite was 8.6 times more effective in photocurrent density than the pure sample. At 0.59 V vs. reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), the highest photon to current conversion efficiency (PCE) achieved was 1.15%, which was 2.05, 2.74, and 5 times higher than pristine BiVO₄, BiVO₄/Ag, and BiVO₄/Cu₂O samples, respectively. Applied bias photon-to-current efficiency (ABPE) values for the corresponding samples (Fig. 9(d)) were found to be 0.23%, 0.42%, 0.56%, and 1.15% for BiVO₄, BiVO₄/Ag, BiVO₄/Cu₂O, and BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O, respectively. The EIS spectra for the optimized sample point toward the lower values of resistance, while bare

Table 2 Comparative performances of BiVO₄-based photoanodes for PEC water splitting

Sr. No.	Electrode material	Electrolyte	Synthesis method	Times increase in performance compared to pure BiVO ₄	Current density J (mA·cm ⁻² at 1.23 V vs. RHE)	Ref.
1.	BiVO ₄ /Bi ₂ S ₃ /NiCoO ₂	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	ED, IE	5.5	2.58	[141]
2.	Mn:FeOOH/BiVO ₄	1 M Na ₂ SO ₃	ED, CBD	2.3	1.40	[142]
3.	BiVO ₄ /Ag/Cu ₂ O	0.2 M Na ₂ SO ₄	HT,CBD, ED	8.6	3.36	[143]
4.	β-FeOOH-B-BiVO ₄	0.5 M borate buffer	ED, WI	3.0	4.96	[144]
5.	NiFe-MOFs/BiVO ₄	0.5 M K ₃ BO ₃	ED	3.0	4.61	[145]
6.	α-Fe ₂ O ₃ /BiVO ₄ /MoS ₂	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	HT, LPE	—	1.67	[146]
7.	BiVO ₄ /MoO ₃	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	RF	6.0	0.22	[147]
8.	Co/BiVO ₄	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	ED, CVD	2.6	2.67	[148]
9.	BiVO ₄ /GQD/g-C ₃ N ₄	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	HT, WI	3.4	19.20 at 1.0 V vs. Ag/AgCl	[149]
10.	Co-Pi/ BiVO ₄ /Cu ₂ O	0.1 M KPi	ED	2.8	2.22	[150]
11.	BiVO ₄ /BPQDs/TiO ₂ /NiOOH	0.5 M KPi + 0.2 M Na ₂ SO ₃	ED	3	6.2	[151]
12.	FeNiPO _x /BiVO ₄	0.5 M KBi	ED	1.77	6.73	[152]
13.	Co-Pi/ BiVO ₄	0.5M phosphate buffer	ED, PED	1.61	6.3	[153]
14.	BiVO ₄ /g-C ₃ N ₄	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄ + Na ₂ SO ₃	SILAR, CVD	2.9	1.14	[154]
15.	NiFe/Fe-BiVO ₄	borate buffer + Na ₂ SO ₃	ED, WI	4.1	6.2	[155]
16.	NiFeO _x /FeVO ₄ /BiVO ₄	0.5 M borate buffer solution	ED, PED	3	5.59	[156]
17.	BiVO ₄ /CuBi ₂ O ₄	0.3 M K ₂ SO ₄ and 0.2 M phosphate buffer	SP	1.82	1.15	[157]
18.	WO ₃ /BiVO ₄	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	ST, SC	—	1.3	[158]
19.	InVO ₄ /BiVO ₄	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	HT	2	0.06 (1 V vs. RHE)	[159]
20.	OH-BiVO ₄ /C/NiFe-LDH	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₃	ED, HT	4.65	5.31	[160]

Figure 9 Top-view SEM images at low and high magnification: (a) BiVO₄, (b) BiVO₄/Ag, and (c) BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O. (d) The calculated ABPEs curves and (e) Nyquist plots. (f) Normalized concentration decay versus time plot for photocatalytic, electrocatalytic, and photoelectrocatalytic degradation of rhodamine B dye on BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O electrode. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [143], © Elsevier B.V. 2021.

BiVO₄ has the highest arc length (Fig. 9(e)) [143]. The degradation efficiency achieved through PEC processes was significantly higher compared to EC or PC processes individually (Fig. 9(f)).

Majumder and Kim devised a BiVO₄/Bi₂S₃/NiCoO₂ composite using a scalable solution process as illustrated in Fig. 10(a). The X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies data (Fig. 10(b)) confirm the existence

of characteristic peaks of all the constituent compound. In contrast, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) studies confirm the existence of the constituent elements in the composite. Additionally, in Fig. 10(b), a nanoworm-like structure can be seen for BiVO₄ with a smooth surface, while NPs of Bi₂S₃ are found to be grown on BiVO₄ in the case of BiVO₄/Bi₂S₃ composite. A rough

Figure 10 (a) Schematic showing the stepwise fabrication of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_3/\text{NiCoO}_2$. (b) XRD and FE-SEM images of BiVO_4 , $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_3$, and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_3/\text{NiCoO}_2$ photoanodes coated over FTO substrate. (c) LSV, (d) ABPE, (e) transient photocurrent density, and (f) the photocurrent stability curves of BiVO_4 , $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_3$, $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_3/\text{NiCoO}_2$ photoanodes measured in 0.5 M of Na_2SO_4 electrolyte, respectively. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [141], © Elsevier B.V. 2021.

surface of BiVO_4 helps with easy diffusion and replacement of ions during the ion exchange process. The PEC measurements revealed that the composite exhibited a five-fold increase in performance compared to bare BiVO_4 as seen in Figs. 10(c)–10(f). There was improved electrolytic stability and charge separation efficiency. The Ni-Co-based oxides are more stable than their constituent oxides, and NiCoO_2 has tetrahedral vacancies that provide three-dimensional (3D) electronic transfer pathways. The choice of coupling of Bi_2S_3 is due to its narrow band gap with a higher absorption coefficient and the alignment of VB being more cathodic, while CB is less anodic than BiVO_4 . Also, this work opens a new avenue for the design of metal oxide/metal chalcogenide/ternary metal oxide-based composites for improved PEC [141]. Z. Masoumi et al. used a similar approach to design $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MoS}_2$ photoelectrode, where the combined morphological effects of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ nanorods and nanosheets of MoS_2 and BiVO_4 intensified the light-harvesting capability. From the multi-heterojunction diagram, it can be seen that due to the difference in the energy levels, easy transfer of electrons in the CB from MoS_2 to BiVO_4 to $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ takes place. Similarly, under the influence of the electrostatic field, the movement of holes in the VB from $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ to BiVO_4 to MoS_2 takes place. This process improves the charge transport and thus helps broaden the visible light absorption by the synthesized catalyst [146].

Identification of the role of hetero-structuring carbon-based compounds like graphene and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ with BiVO_4 to improve the structural and optical properties was studied by M. Samsudin and co-researchers. A comparative study of electron mediator using reduced graphene oxide (rGO) and graphene quantum dots (GQDs) for $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ composite was carried out. Field emission-scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) images of the three samples $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{RGO}/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{GQD}/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ are shown in Figs. 11(a)–11(c). BiVO_4 microflower is seen in all three cases, while the two-dimensional (2D) crumpled porous structure of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ is randomly distributed on the surface of BiVO_4 . Zoomed-in images of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{RGO}/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ show rGO nanosheets disorderly stacked. But the detection of GQDs is not so precise from FE-SEM, and hence, high resolution (HR)-TEM for the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{GQD}/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ was carried out, which clearly shows the existence of GQDs having a diameter in the range of 5 to 9 nm (see Fig. 11(d)). DFT calculations and experimental results validated that the substitution of GQDs electron mediator outperformed rGO in PEC performances. Essentially, without sacrificial reagents, the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{GQDs}/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ ternary composite delivered a very high photocurrent density of $19.2 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. To theoretically explain this behavior, a partial DOS analysis was carried out. It was seen that for the GQD-ternary composite, the hybridization of the orbitals of N, Bi, V, C, and O atoms is the

Figure 11 FE-SEM micrograph images of (a) BiVO₄/g-C₃N₄, (b) BiVO₄/RGO/g-C₃N₄ (inset is the 200 nm zoom micrograph image which detects the RGO layer in the composite sample), (c) BiVO₄/GQD/g-C₃N₄, and (d) HRTEM image of GQD. (e) Energy level diagram of the band edge positions of BiVO₄, BiVO₄/g-C₃N₄, BiVO₄/RGO/g-C₃N₄, and BiVO₄/GQD/g-C₃N₄. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [149], © Elsevier Inc. 2020.

strongest due to stronger overlapping compared to other samples. This finding correlates well with the experimental data. Accordingly, band edge positions of all the photocatalysts are schematically presented in Fig. 11(e). Two trends are observed in the schematics: (i) Heterostructure formation shifts the band edge positions and the Fermi energy level to the optimum redox potential values, (ii) BiVO₄/GQD/g-C₃N₄ shows the most prominent band edge potential and change in Fermi level required for high values of PEC activity [149].

Another approach that seems to be promising and has been investigated for different applications is the co-catalyst technique [161, 162]. The co-catalysts are further categorized into p-type or n-type. Han et al. demonstrated that using Mn-FeOOH as a p-type co-catalyst with BiVO₄ improves the photocurrent density response by 2.3 times than the bare photoanode [142]. Also, OER kinetics is found to be substantially enhanced as the cocatalyst accelerates the charge transfer process by surface passivation, and electron-hole recombination is suppressed. A similar report has been published

by Kang and co-workers [144], wherein β-FeOOH nanolayer was anchored on borate-post-treated nanoporous BiVO₄ to obtain β-FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanode (Fig. 12(a)). Also, SEM images reveal the uniform dispersion of worm-like grains of BiVO₄ on FTO (Figs. 12(b)–12(e)). The borate modification does not induce any noticeable morphological change in BiVO₄, but for the β-FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanode, the surface appears rougher compared to the other samples. β-FeOOH provides abundant oxygen vacancies while the borate treatment provides [B(OH)₄]⁻ ligands that act as passivator layers to inhibit the electron-hole recombination, promoting surficial hole extraction. Thus, these factors significantly contributed to the highest photocurrent response, incident photon to conversion efficiency (IPCE), and STH efficiency values for β-FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanode (Figs. 12(f)–12(i)). To verify the long-term steadiness of the photocurrent densities, the photoanodes were tested in the 0.5 M potassium borate solution with the addition of 0.1 M NaVO₃. When the tests were carried out in KB solution alone, the photo

Figure 12 (a) Schematic illustration of the synthesis of β -FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanode. The SEM images of (b) BiOI, (c) BiVO₄, (d) B-BiVO₄, and (e) β -FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanodes. (f) LSV curves of photoanodes under AM 1.5 G simulated sunlight at 100 mW·cm⁻² in a 0.5 M borate buffer (pH = 9.3), scan rate: 10 mV·s⁻¹. (g) Photocurrent density versus time of the photoanodes measured at 1.23 V vs. RHE under AM 1.5 G illumination in 0.5 M borate buffer (pH = 9.3). (h) HC-STHs of BiVO₄, B-BiVO₄, and β -FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanodes measured at 1.23 V vs. RHE. (i) IPCEs of BiVO₄, B-BiVO₄, and β -FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanodes measured at 1.23 V vs. RHE. (j) and (k) SEM images of β -FeOOH-B-BiVO₄ photoanodes before and after testing stability. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [144], © Elsevier B.V. 2021.

corrosion was very high, declining performance to 37% of the initial value in just 10 h. However, the addition of the NaVO_3 helped prevent loss associated with the dissolution of VO_4^{3-} ions and thus provides long-term stability. It was found that the decay rate was about 87% of the maximum value after 20 h of illumination at a constant potential of 1.23 V vs. RHE. The surface morphology also remained relatively similar, thus broadening our understanding in the role of adjusting electrolytic composition for long term stabilities (see Figs. 12(j) and 12(k)). The increasing importance of MOFs in energy storage devices and similar applications cannot be understated. Li et al. designed NiFe-MOFs as cocatalysts for BiVO_4 photoanode. The performance improvement is a key role of several factors, and a prominent reason is the oxidation of the Ni^{2+} in NiFe-MOFs to higher valence states like Ni^{3+} or Ni^{4+} via photo-induced hole trapping that serves as a leading catalytic site, whereas reduction of Ni^{4+} to Ni^{2+} lowers the recombination of charge carriers and thereby improving solar water oxidation [145].

Recently, 2D MXenes, composed of early transition metal carbides/nitrides, that serve as conductive supports or electrocatalysts with oxygen-terminated functional groups have been widely investigated [163]. In a study, MXene/ BiVO_4 / FeOOH composite, synthesized by P. Liu and colleagues, was investigated to understand its charge transfer mechanism and its effect on PEC activity. The study incorporated oxygen vacancies in FeOOH , significantly enhancing water oxidation kinetics. MXene served as a highly conductive framework, suppressing carrier recombination within the composite. This material exhibited a remarkable photocurrent density of $4.95 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE, representing a 4.1-fold increase compared to bare BiVO_4 . The enhanced PEC performance was attributed to synergistic effects arising from optimized band alignment and a built-in electric field, collectively improving charge separation efficiency [164]. In another study, a Co-MOF/MXene/ BiVO_4 composite photoanode was fabricated using a spin-coating technique combined with chemical bath deposition. Integrating MXene and Co-MOF significantly improved the PEC performance of bare BiVO_4 . This composite achieved a high photocurrent density of $4.26 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE, a 4.7-fold increase over the $0.90 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ obtained with pure BiVO_4 . Additionally, it exhibited a cathodic shift of 357 mV compared to bare BiVO_4 , an ABPE of 1.78% at 0.589 V vs. RHE, and an IPCE of 76.7% at 420 nm, along with an impressive charge injection efficiency of 92.2%. The enhanced PEC performance of the Co-MOF/MXene/ BiVO_4 composite was attributed to MXene's role in introducing a strong built-in electric field within BiVO_4 , providing an additional driving force for charge carrier transfer. This significantly reduced bulk recombination losses and improved charge separation efficiency. The synergy between MXene's excellent conductivity and Co-MOF's catalytic properties enhanced light absorption and charge transport, resulting in superior PEC activity [165].

Samsudin and colleagues demonstrated that the BiVO_4 /GQD/g- C_3N_4 composite exhibits the highest current density among BiVO_4 -based materials reported in the literature for PEC application. This greater performance is due to the GQDs within the composite, which act as efficient electron mediators. Due to their small diameter, GQDs induce a minor shift in the Fermi level just above the conduction band, effectively reducing electron-hole recombination rates and promoting faster charge transfer. Importantly, this composite achieves a high PEC performance at a relatively low overpotential of 1 V vs. RHE in a 0.5 M Na_2SO_4

electrolyte solution [149]. In addition, carbon nitride-based heterojunctions show promising PEC activity due to their capacity for bandgap tuning and the formation of Z-scheme structures. This Z-scheme structure results in an effective reduction of the bandgap, which extends the visible light absorption range and improves light-harvesting efficiency [154, 166]. Consequently, these heterojunctions display enhanced PEC performance by facilitating a more effective separation of charge carriers and improved photocatalytic efficiency. Sulfide-based heterojunctions, particularly those involving Bi_2S_3 , have also been explored for their PEC enhancement potential. The narrow bandgap of Bi_2S_3 enables enhanced light absorption, while the favorable alignment of its valence and conduction bands with respect to BiVO_4 promotes efficient charge transfer phenomenon in $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_3$ heterojunction. As a result, Bi_2S_3 -based heterojunctions significantly improve PEC performance through an optimized band alignment [141]. Moreover, the plot highlights significant PEC performance enhancements in materials based on MOFs and MoS_2 , indicating the potential of these materials for PEC applications due to their unique structural and electronic properties [145, 146].

Other strategies like morphology and facet engineering [153, 167], electrochemical environment [168], carrier diffusion layer modification [169], facet-cocatalyst mixed approach [170] etc., are being potentially explored. Thus, enormous efforts have been taken to improve the solar hydrogen production capacity of BiVO_4 using the PEC process. As discussed, different techniques like doping, coupling, heterojunction formations [171], etc., have been applied to enhance efficiencies. The research in this field is still in its nascent stages, and greater exploration of new strategies is required for industrial-scale hydrogen production. Most of the work is focused on type-II heterojunction systems or doping, while other suitable schemes like Z-scheme or formation of hybrid systems still need to be explored. The selection of emerging materials compatible with our needs should be investigated based on theoretical insights using DFT calculations. Also, integrating different device structures to form a tandem cell configuration could be explored for standalone overall water splitting [172]. Additionally, the design of photoelectrodes for solar hydrogen generation from seawater that have long-term stability, are anti-corrosive and have higher efficiencies needs to be explored further [20].

3.2 Wastewater treatment using photocatalytic BiVO_4

Generally, in photocatalytic activity, photons-light energy of higher energy ($E > E_{\text{BC}}$) is absorbed by semiconductor photocatalysts, which results in the formation of electrons (e^-) in the CB and the formation of holes (h^+) in the VB. The redox reaction is promoted by excited photogenerated charge carriers due to their migration to the surface of the photocatalyst. Due to the reaction between electrons, holes, and H_2O , superoxide radical anions such as (O_2^-) and hydroxyl radicals (OH^\cdot) are generated. Their oxidation and reduction potential are so strong they can decompose aqueous toxins. The chemical reactions that take place during photocatalysis are as follows

Wastewater contains high levels of organic pollutants. Organic pollutants have a variety of toxic materials, and this toxicity cannot be entirely and easily minimized. Hence, various physical and chemical methods are extensively investigated to solve this problem. One of the techniques to reduce environmental pollution is the electrochemical method. This versatile method has powerful oxidation and high efficiency [173]. The advanced electrochemical oxidation is dimensionally stable with highly efficient anodes and electrodes showing effective oxidation and good efficiency, such as platinum, graphite, RuO_2 , IrO_2 , boron-doped diamond electrodes, etc. [174]. Here, only electrons are utilized instead of chemicals, offering a sustainable energy-environmental strategy for simultaneous hydrogen production during the treatment of organic pollutants [175]. Treating the wastewater is aided by bacteria that consume the organic matter and simultaneously generate electricity. Through PEC cells, solar energy can be harnessed to form clean hydrogen fuels by PEC reactions without involving any additional inputs [176]. Sunlight degrades organic and metallic pollutants in wastewater using solar-charged photoelectrochemical wastewater fuel cells (scPEWFC), which simultaneously detect total organic carbon (TOC) and produce hydrogen for energy. Thus, using water splitting phenomena in the presence of light sources such as UV light/sunlight, sustainable and energy-efficient production of hydrogen can be achieved in the dark without an external power supply. Also, using the new application scPEWFC enhances long-lasting and stable green energy production routes in the energy field and environment [177]. Organic waste contaminants can be considered suitable electron donors and can be successfully used to reduce biological sulfate. This can be seen as an ideal available hydrogen energy source [178].

3.2.1 Dye degradation

Dye industries are considered among the most toxic due to the release of hazardous dye products from textile industries. In many sectors, organic dyes are widely used in cosmetics, printing, leather, plastic, etc. Seventy percent of globally generated wastewater is not pre-treated before discharging to natural water bodies. Not all the dye molecules are used during the dyeing process; hence, the water waste released by the dye industry is contained. Hence, the water waste released by the dye industry contains a considerable percentage of these dye molecules. Also, it is critical to remove dyes from wastewater before they are discharged into the external environment. Due to complex aromatic molecular structures, organic dyes are not fully degradable in conventional wastewater treatment techniques.

Dye degradation is when large dye molecules are chemically broken down into smaller molecules. Hence, various processes are developed depending on their merits and limitations. The adsorption process is one of the promising methods for removing dyes due to its efficiency, wide adaptability, easy operation, and simple design [179]. Dye molecules unreactive to light, oxygen, acids, and bases require degradation through photocatalysis using a UV-visible light source, a widely accepted environmental purification. During photocatalysis, superoxide anions and hydroxyl radicals are formed through the reaction of electron-hole pairs with oxygen and water molecules. They have increased

oxidizing and reducing abilities and can be used on numerous industrial dye compounds. The most studied dyes for photocatalysis are thiazine dyes (having dominance of methylene blue: 37% of all papers on thiazines), second is xanthenes (having dominance of rhodamine B: 30% of all papers on xanthenes). Azo dyes dominate the global production of about 50%–70% of the market, contributing to environmental challenges, yet come only fourth in studies [180]. Using photocatalysts such as TiO_2 , ZnO , BiVO_4 , etc., an environmentally friendly, non-expensive degradation of dyes can be achieved by targeting the main aim of treating wastewater.

BiVO_4 NPs exhibit photocatalytic activity for the degradation of various dyes. Common dyes such as MB, rhodamine blue (RhB), malachite green (MG), methyl orange (MO), congo red (CR), acid orange (AO), and crystal violet (CV) are effectively degraded under visible light irradiation under ambient conditions. When semiconducting materials are exposed to light irradiation, a photocatalytic process happens. The reactions generally proceed with photogenerated electron-hole pairs. The reactions are as follows

Water molecules interact with holes to form OH^\cdot (hydroxyl radicals) at the valence band

In addition, from generated photoelectrons at the conduction band, oxygen reduction (superoxide radicals) occurs as

These hydroxyl and superoxide radicals interact with dye molecules and, through several reaction steps, degrade the dyes to produce water and carbon dioxide as final products [181].

From Table 3, we can see that different BiVO_4 -based composites are used to degrade common industrial dyes. The processes and strategies of some of these observations are discussed below. Zhang et al. have made 2D single crystal nanosheets of BiVO_4 with ~10–40 nm thickness by using the HT route in the presence of surfactant-dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS). Synthesized nanosheets of BiVO_4 in the presence of SDBS were then combined with rGO for improving the performance of photodegradation of dyes such as RhB and MG [182]. It was found that an optimized amount of rGO content was significant for higher photodegradation performance. Many researchers have found that the photocatalytic activity of BiVO_4 can be enhanced by doping metals such as Ag, Fe, and Ni, as well as metal oxides like WO_3 , Cu_2O , and Ag_2O , on the surface of BiVO_4 . This increment was reported because of the suppression of photoelectrons and hole recombination at photocatalyst interfaces [183]. The rGO increases the surface area and transportability. The mesoporous nature of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{N-rGO}$ facilitates the accessibility of pollutant molecules toward the photocatalyst. Appavu and co-workers found that the effective separation of photo-induced electron-hole pairs and a faster interfacial charge transfer is because of the small radius of $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{N-rGO}$. The unique two-dimensional π conjugation and high electrical conductivity of graphene help to transfer the photogenerated electrons by BiVO_4 rapidly [184].

Other 2D materials like MXenes and hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) have been explored for their beneficial properties when

Table 3 Degradation of industrial dyes by BiVO₄-based materials under visible light

Sr. No.	Material	Dye	Efficiency (% degradation)	Time (min)	Rate constant (min ⁻¹)	Ref.
1.	BiVO ₄	Acid orange 7	88	90	0.0160	[187]
2.	Co ₃ O ₄ /BiVO ₄	Acid orange II	86	300	—	[188]
3.	BiVO ₄ /Fe ₃ O ₄	Acid red B	97.6	40	0.0427	[189]
4.	BiVO ₄	Alzarin red S	99.6	180	0.0228	[190]
5.	BiVO ₄ /N-rGO	Congo red	95	90	0.0436	[184]
6.	BiVO ₄	Crystal violet	96.23	120	0.0173	[191]
7.	BiVO ₄	Crystal violet	95.65	60	—	[192]
8.	BiVO ₄	Malachite green	77.29	120	0.0095	[182]
9.	BiVO ₄	Methylene blue	91.9	90	0.0197	[43]
10.	BiVO ₄ /N-rGO	Methylene blue	98	90	0.0340	[184]
11.	Co-BiVO ₄	Methylene blue	85	200	—	[193]
12.	BiVO ₄	Methylene blue	86	80	—	[194]
13.	BiVO ₄	Methylene blue	91	60	0.00388	[195]
14.	BiVO ₄	Methylene blue	72	240	0.00524	[196]
15.	rGO/BiVO ₄	Methylene blue	96.9	190	—	[197]
16.	Mo-doped BiVO ₄	Methylene blue	96	180	0.0440	[198]
17.	Yb-BiVO ₄ /Bi ₂ O ₃	Methyl orange	93.3	120	—	[199]
18.	CNP/B- BiVO ₄ /WO ₃	Orange 2	56	180	0.0140	[200]
19.	BiVO ₄	Rhodamine B	64.94	120	0.0068	[182]
20.	BiVO ₄ -rGO	Rhodamine B	99.84	20	0.0264	[182]
21.	EG -BiVO ₄ /ZnO	Rhodamine B	91	240	0.0092	[201]
22.	BiVO ₄	Rhodamine B	99.3	210	—	[202]
23.	BiVO ₄ /WO ₃	Rhodamine B	81.6	360	0.0047	[203]
24.	BiVO ₄ /TiO ₂	Rhodamine B	94	300	—	[204]
25.	Fe ₂ O ₃ /BiVO ₄	Rhodamine B	97	40	0.086	[205]

combined with BiVO₄, enhancing photocatalytic degradation efficiency and stability. A BiVO₄/MXene composite, synthesized by M. M. Sajid and collaborators via a HT method, was investigated for the PC degradation of MO and CR. The composite achieved a degradation efficiency of 99.5% for MO within 60 min and 99.1% for CR within 130 min, attributed to several factors, including the composite's large surface area, a reduced bandgap of 1.99 eV compared to bare BiVO₄, and efficient electron-hole pair separation facilitated by MXene [185]. BiVO₄/h-BN nanocomposites achieved degradation efficiencies of 93.3% for RhB and 92.9% for CR under visible light. CR degradation involves the breakdown of sulfonate groups and azo bonds, producing intermediates with *m/z* values of 650, 325, 443, 307, 258, 213, 205, 171, and 143. These intermediates degrade into smaller compounds (*m/z* = 93, 157, 77) and oxidize into acetic acid, malonate, and alcohols. Ultimately, complete mineralization generates NO₃⁻, CO₂, NH₄⁺, and H₂O. Photodegradation of RhB by ·OH radicals targets the dye's central carbon, cleaving the azo bond (*m/z* = 415) and forming intermediates (*m/z* = 387, 230) through sequential bond cleavage and N-de-ethylation. The final products, lacking chromophores, are decolorized and mineralized into H₂O, CO₂, and harmless organic compounds [186].

An emerging strategy that has received considerable attention in most of the applications and is gaining momentum is PEC-assisted degradation. For this, Ma et al. synthesized ternary composite

BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O using HT and CBD methods. The SPR effect of Ag NPs and a p-n heterojunction scheme of BiVO₄/Cu₂O considerably improved the overall performance compared to bare BiVO₄. Figures 9(a)–9(c) shows the SEM images of the as-synthesized samples. Pristine BiVO₄ shows a compact nanosheet structure, while the Ag NPs are scattered on its surface. The cubic nanocubes of Cu₂O encompass the Ag/BiVO₄ photoelectrode. To compare the PEC phenomenon with photochemical and electrochemical, the degradation of RhB was carried out at 1.2 V vs. RHE. To test the feasibility and the performances of the electrodes, the PEC studies of BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O were carried out in 0.2 M Na₂SO₄ (pH = 6.5) under a solar simulator. It can be seen that (Fig. 9(d)) the ABPE and current density of the samples is highest for BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O. The other samples in decreasing order of the performances are, BiVO₄/Cu₂O, BiVO₄/Ag, and BiVO₄. Also, the EIS spectra fitting curve reveals that the final optimized composite has the lowest values of charge transfer resistance (*R*_{ct}). Thus, lower resistance, the synergistic effect of heterojunction, local electric field generation due to the SPR effect, and the p-n type combination collectively boosted the overall performance of the BiVO₄/Ag/Cu₂O composite. Figure 9(f) shows that the degradation rate is the highest for the PEC process (86% within 120 min), followed by electrochemical and photochemical. Thus, the work opens a new possibility of utilizing the PEC process for degradation studies to extend the photocatalytic mechanism for wastewater treatment

[143]. The PEC assisted MB degradation process, was carried out using the Ni-doped PbS quantum dots on $\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$. The liquid chromatography-mass chromatography (LC-MS) reveals that MB (mass to charge ratio, $m/z = 284$) degradation begins with the cleavage of the N- CH_3 bond due to its low bond dissociation energy ($70.8 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), forming intermediates like 3-(dimethylamino)-7-(methylamino)phenothiazine-5-ium ($m/z = 270$) and subsequent derivatives. Hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and ozone (O_3) attacks further degrade MB, leading to end products such as benzenesulfonic acid ($m/z = 159$), 4-nitroaniline ($m/z = 138$), phenol ($m/z = 94$), NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_2 , and H_2O [206].

3.2.2 Pharmaceutical wastewater treatment

One of the biggest groups of emerging contaminants is pharmaceutical or biomedical waste consumed in large quantities worldwide. These contaminants, such as ciprofloxacin (CIP), ibuprofen, metronidazole, amoxicillin, etc., in water, pose a threatening effect on the environment and human health [207]. Biological treatment is commonly and effectively used in wastewater treatment to remove contaminants. Yet, these processes cannot entirely remove toxic and refractory organic pollutants. Photocatalytic oxidation emerges as a promising technique due to its non-toxicity, relatively low cost, chemical stability, and possible operation at ambient temperature. The optimum catalyst concentration is used to avoid the decrease in process efficiency and reduction in contaminant removal efficiency [208].

L. Wang et al. [209] reported the degradation of paracetamol by Pd-BiVO₄ with an extended absorption edge at 550 nm and 100% removal efficiency. Compared to Pd or Pt, other metals such as Cu or Ag are mostly used because of their low cost and ease of availability. The photocatalytic activity of Ag or Cu-loaded BiVO₄ showed enhancement because of the low recombination of photogenerated electron and holes pair. When BiVO₄ as an n-type semiconductor and copper oxide as a p-type semiconductor were loaded, p-n heterojunction formed, which boosted their photocatalytic activity [210, 211]. Thus, Ag/Ag₂O or Cu/Cu₂O coating lowers the band gap energy, improves the visible light response, and enhances the light-responsive edge. The coating of the metals also helps roughen the surface of BiVO₄, thus improving the scattering effect [212]. Chen et al. [213] utilized the Z scheme heterojunction strategy and synthesized ternary Ag/AgBr/BiVO₄ composite for simultaneous CIP oxidation and Cr(VI) reduction studies. AgBr was selected due to its photosensitive character wherein, under visible light irradiation, Ag⁺ in AgBr converts to Ag⁰ and demonstrates SPR. Different weight ratios ($x = 0, 12.5\%, 25.0\%$, and 37.5%) of AgBr with BiVO₄ were synthesized and labeled as ABBV- x . From the SEM images of pure BiVO₄, Ag/AgBr, and Ag/AgBr/BiVO₄, it was observed that pure BiVO₄ shows smooth nanosheet morphology while Ag/AgBr consisted of smaller NPs of varying sizes (50–600 nm). However, in the ternary composite, the size of these Ag/AgBr NPs became smaller, which could result from lower particle agglomeration in the composite. The EDS and TEM images do confirm the existence of the constituent elements and successful loading of Ag/AgBr on BiVO₄ nanosheets. The simultaneous photocatalytic degradation experiments of CIP and Cr(VI) reduction were carried out under visible light. Out of the different combinations, ABBV-25 exhibited the highest degradation performance for both pollutants. The rate constant for degradation of CIP in the increasing order was calculated to be $\text{BiVO}_4 < \text{Ag/AgBr} < \text{ABBV-12.5} < \text{ABBV-37.5} < \text{ABBV-25.0}$. The

photocurrent response of each sample further confirmed the results. Also, radical trapping studies were carried out to understand the role of different scavengers in the degradation. Disodium ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA-2Na), benzoquinone (BQ), and tert-butyl alcohol (TBA) were used as quenchers of h^+ , $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, and $\cdot\text{OH}$, respectively. It was identified that all three radicals actively participated in the degradation, while h^+ and $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ had significant roles. LC-MS of the resulting solution was carried out to get better insight into the products obtained after the degradation of CIP and to understand the degradation pathway. Based on the intermediate products obtained from LC-MS data, three different pathways for the degradation of CIP were proposed.

In another work, Yan et al. [214] fabricated a heterostructure of BiVO₄ with BiPO₄ using an anion exchange method. Different weight percent combinations with BiVO₄ were carried out. The choice of BiPO₄ was primarily due to its more excellent UV light photocatalytic compared to commonly used TiO₂. Also, PO₄³⁻ anions present in the compound show an inductive effect that helps better separate holes and electrons. Figures 13(a)–13(f) show the morphology of samples with different amounts of VO₄³⁻ ions during the heterojunction formation of BiVO₄/BiPO₄. Initially, the morphology of pure BiPO₄ is that of several rhomboidal-shaped bricks with smooth surfaces, while pure BiVO₄ displays a cuboidal shape. Increasing the content of VO₄³⁻ ions retains the original morphology of BiPO₄ with a slight increase in surface roughness. As more ions are added, a point reaches where the brick-like morphology collapses and turns into uniform NPs. Figures 13(g) and 13(h) help to understand this morphological evolution of the composite of BiVO₄/BiPO₄. When the samples were tested for metronidazole (MNZ) degradation, the 25% BiVO₄/BiPO₄ composite delivered the highest performance (90% in 120 min) under UV light. In contrast, in visible light, MB, RhB, phenol, and MNZ degradation rates reached 88.1%, 98.3%, 75.4%, and 66.5% in 360 min, respectively. The photocurrent intensity of the optimized sample considerably improves, while EIS spectra show a lowering of resistance. Also, it is seen for 25% BiVO₄/BiPO₄ composite that the UV-DRS has a greater area lying under the visible spectrum while its PL spectra cover the minimum area under the curve.

The Z-scheme photocatalyst BiVO₄/g-C₃N₄/Au NPs were investigated for the degradation of duloxetine (DLX), an antidepressant. The composite exhibited a fourfold enhancement in the rate constant compared to bare BiVO₄. The proposed degradation pathways suggest that DLX is broken down into simpler aliphatic compounds via the cleavage of aromatic rings, effectively reducing its potential toxicity to model organisms such as *Selenastrum ambiguum* and *Aliivibrio fischeri* [215]. A BiVO₄/graphene photocatalyst exhibited high PC activity for degrading sulfamethoxazole (SMX) antibiotic under blue LED light, achieving 57% degradation in the first cycle. After four reuse cycles (8 h each), the degradation efficiency slightly decreased to 55%, 54.5%, and 53.4% in subsequent cycles, demonstrating stable activity. Toxicity analysis using *Vibrio fischeri* showed a 37.53% bioluminescence inhibition before photocatalysis, which reduced by 25% after 480 min, indicating a significant reduction in toxicity despite incomplete SMX degradation, as supported by TOC measurements [216].

A study on the synergistic interaction between ozone-nanobubbles and the ZnFe₂O₄/BiVO₄/rGO heterojunction revealed a 20% improvement in oxytetracycline (OTC) degradation efficiency. At optimal conditions (pH 7.0, catalyst concentration of

Figure 13 SEM images of the as-prepared samples: (a) pure BiPO₄, (b) BiVO₄/BiPO₄ (BVP)-0.1, (c) BVP-0.25, (e) BVP-0.5, (f) BVP-1, and (d) EDS spectrum of BVP-0.25. (g) The morphology evolution process with SEM images, and (h) the schematic of the morphology evolution process of the BiVO₄/BiPO₄ composites. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [214], © Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers 2019.

0.5 g·L⁻¹, and OTC concentration of 20 mg·L⁻¹, 96.3% degradation was achieved within 100 min. The degradation efficiency remained above 80% after four reuse cycles, demonstrating excellent catalyst stability. LC-MS analysis of OTC degradation by the ZnFe₂O₄/BiVO₄/rGO photocatalyst with ozone-NBs revealed a sequential pathway involving demethylation, fragmentation, ring opening, dehydration, and decarboxylation. Intermediates (OTC1–OTC10) were identified, further breaking down into smaller organic molecules (OTC11, OTC12) and ultimately mineralizing into CO₂, H₂O, and NO₃⁻. This demonstrates OTC's effective degradation and mineralization into non-toxic byproducts

[217]. Tetracycline hydrochloride (TCH) was effectively degraded using the ZnIn₂S₄/BiVO₄ photocatalyst, achieving degradation rates 1.4 times higher than BiVO₄ and 1.1 times higher than ZnIn₂S₄ alone. The degradation pathways of TCH (*m/z* = 481) were proposed based on LC-MS analysis and existing literature. During the process, TCH undergoes dechlorination, converting into tetracycline (TC, *m/z* = 445) by losing an HCl molecule in an aqueous medium. In one pathway, hydroxylation and deamidation reactions form hydroxylated and ring-opened intermediates via carbon–carbon bond cleavage and oxidative transformations. In another path, hydroxylation, demethylation, and benzene ring

cleavage generate additional intermediates, which are ultimately mineralized into non-toxic end products such as CO_2 , H_2O , and NH_4^+ by reactive oxygen species (ROS) [218]. The degradation of imidacloprid (IMD) by $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}/\text{BiVO}_4$ composites was analyzed using LC-MS, revealing pathways involving $\cdot\text{OH}$ and ROS. IMD undergoes nitro group decomposition, hydroxylation, and bond cleavage, forming intermediates that are eventually mineralized into non-toxic products such as H_2O , CO_2 , NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , and Cl^- under sustained PC activity [219].

A $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{h-BN}$ nanocomposite, with a bandgap of 2 eV, effectively degraded water-polluting dyes and antibiotics, achieving 94.1% and 90.1% degradation of amoxicillin (AMX) and cephalixin (CPX) under visible light within 60 min. The PC degradation of CPX involves hydroxylation, decarboxylation, demethylation, and de-alkylation, breaking CPX molecules into smaller fragments. Key intermediates include $m/z = 386.67$ (β -lactam ring opening), $m/z = 370.72$ and 327.88 (via de-carboxylation and de-alkylation), and final fragments $m/z = 192.72$ and 139.93 , formed through C–N cleavage, yielding CO_2 and water. The degradation of AMX initiates with the formation of amoxicillin penicillanic acid ($m/z = 383$), followed by deamination and decarboxylation, resulting in intermediates at $m/z = 368$ and 339 . Subsequent hydroxylation and further deamination lead to the formation of $m/z = 324$, with bond cleavage of the β -lactam ring yielding $m/z = 176$, which is ultimately mineralized to H_2O and CO_2 [186].

BiVO_4 was utilized for tetracycline (TET) degradation under optimal conditions (pH 9 and enriched dissolved oxygen), achieving 96% efficiency with a rate constant of 0.1069 min^{-1} . The process predominantly involved ROS, particularly O_2^- , as key contributors to TET degradation. Under blue LED light, PC degradation of TET produces intermediate by-products identified via HPLC-MS with m/z values of 429, 417, 387, 372, 358, 248, 179, and 127. The degradation pathway involves hydroxyl radical attacks leading to deamination, demethylation, and cleavage of functional

groups, progressively breaking down TET into simpler intermediates. Ultimately, these intermediates mineralize into non-toxic molecules like CO_2 and H_2O . Toxicological profiling using the ECOSAR predictive model, aligned with the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS, Revision 10, 2023), revealed varying toxicities of TET and its intermediates. The results indicate minimal acute toxicity to fish but the highest acute toxicity to algae. Scalability and stability were assessed using a slurry bubble column reactor (SBCR), ensuring uniform nanoparticle suspension, efficient oxygen transfer, and superior catalyst utilization. This energy-efficient setup outperforms conventional methods, demonstrating high potential for large-scale water pollution treatment [220].

Additional studies on the degradation of various compounds, such as ibuprofen [221], levofloxacin [222, 223], Naproxen [224], sulfonamide antibiotics (sulfadimeisoxazole and sulfadimidine) [225], quinolone antibiotics (ofloxacin and lomefloxacin) [225], and sulfamethoxazole [226], as well as the intermediates formed during degradation and their proposed degradation pathways, are available in the literature. Table 4 shows the degradation of pharmaceutical compounds by pure and doped BiVO_4 compounds and the degradation of pharmaceutical waste through the absorption of various light sources to remove emerging contaminants in water.

3.2.3 Reduction of organic compounds

Degradation of organic compounds by the technique of semiconductor photocatalysis has become an attractive research area in photochemistry over the past two decades. Organic compounds can be reduced because of their direct UV–vis light absorption. Table 5 contains information on some of the organic compounds degraded by BiVO_4 -based materials under visible irradiation. K. M. Shaku et al. studied the photo redox reactions using a photocatalytic membrane consisting of NPs and BiVO_4 hyperbranched polyethyleneimine (HBPE) blended in polyether

Table 4 Degradation of pharmaceutical compounds by BiVO_4 -based materials under visible light

Sr. No.	Material	Pharmaceutical compound	Efficiency (% degradation)	Time (min)	Rate constant (min^{-1})	Ref.
1.	BiVO_4	Amoxicillin	98.6	90	—	[227]
2.	$\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}/\text{BiVO}_4$	Carbamazepine	70.6	240	—	[228]
3.	$\text{BiVO}_4/\text{N-rGO}$	Chloramphenicol	93	300	0.0091	[184]
4.	BiVO_4	Ciprofloxacin	58.55	120	0.0083	[213]
5.	$\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MnO}_2$	Ciprofloxacin	76	120	0.0105	[229]
6.	BiVO_4	Ciprofloxacin	22.7	60	—	[230]
7.	rGO/BiVO_4	Ciprofloxacin	68.2	60	—	[230]
8.	$\text{Fe}/\text{BiOCl}/\text{BiVO}_4$	Ciprofloxacin	96.5	75	0.03920	[231]
9.	$\text{SnS}_2/\text{BiVO}_4$	Ciprofloxacin	92	105	0.0184	[232]
10.	$\text{F-BiVO}_4/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4/\text{CdS}$	Ciprofloxacin	90	30	0.06455	[233]
11.	BiVO_4	Ibuprofen	45	300	0.0020	[211]
12.	Cu/BiVO_4	Ibuprofen	89	300	0.0080	[211]
13.	Ag/BiVO_4	Ibuprofen	96	300	0.0110	[211]
14.	N-doped BiVO_4	Ibuprofen	90	5.75	0.0131	[234]
15.	Fe/BiVO_4	Ibuprofen	80	180	—	[235]
16.	$\text{BiVO}_4/\text{N-rGO}$	Metronidazole	95	240	0.0124	[184]
17.	$\text{BiVO}_4/\text{BiPO}_4$	Metronidazole	90	120	—	[214]
18.	BiVO_4	Metronidazole	97	90	0.0230	[227]

(Continued)

Sr. No.	Material	Pharmaceutical compound	Efficiency (% degradation)	Time (min)	Rate constant (min^{-1})	Ref.
19.	$\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{BiVO}_4$	Metronidazole	92.2	180	0.0303	[236]
20.	BiVO_4	Metronidazole	40	90	—	[237]
21.	S&W co-doped BiVO_4	Naproxen	76.5	180	0.0067	[238]
22.	Pd/BiVO_4	Paracetamol	100	60	—	[209]
23.	BiVO_4	Paracetamol	95	300	—	[239]
24.	Ag/BiVO_4	Paracetamol	77.9	300	—	[240]
25.	$\text{Cu}_3\text{P}/\text{BiVO}_4$	Sulfamethoxazole	82	120	0.0141	[241]
26.	BiVO_4	Tetracycline	96	60	0.0290	[242]
27.	$\text{MoS}_2/\text{BiVO}_4$	Tetracycline	93.7	90	0.0215	[243]
28.	$\text{MnO}_2/\text{BiVO}_4$	Tetracycline	59	120	0.040	[244]

Table 5 Degradation of organic compounds by BiVO_4 -based materials under visible light

Sr. No.	Material	Organic compound	Efficiency (% degradation)	Time (min)	Rate constant (min^{-1})	Ref.
1	$\text{Ag}/\text{CuInS}_2/\text{BiVO}_4$	Bisphenol A	98.8	180	—	[247]
2	BiVO_4	Chlorite (ClO_2^-)	23	30	—	[248]
3	BiVO_4	Cr(IV)	100	180	0.01626	[249]
4	BiVO_4	Cr(VI)	70.3	—	0.0211	[213]
5	$\text{Cu}-\text{BiVO}_4$	Phenol	93	360	—	[250]
6	BiVO_4	2,4-Dichlorophenol	60	300	—	[210]
7	$\text{Co}-\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3$	2-Mercaptobenzothiazole	97.7	40	0.0857	[251]
8	BiVO_4	Phenol	10	100	—	[252]
9	$\text{BiVO}_4/\text{BiPO}_4$	Phenol	75.4	360	—	[214]
10	BiVO_4	Phenol	100	90	—	[245]
11	BiVO_4	p-Chlorophenol	78.50	180	0.00629	[253]
12	$\text{BiVO}_4/\text{PANI}$	p-Nitrophenol	98.5	240	0.0072	[254]
13	$\text{HPEI}/\text{BiVO}_4$	Triclosan phenol	86	60	0.0259	[245]
14	BiVO_4	Toluene	55	360	—	[97]

sulfone for phenol degradation. They concluded that the highest photodegradation rate for phenol was observed at higher loading of BiVO_4 (0.3% and 0.5%) after only 90 min of degradation [245]. This indicates that the presence of BiVO_4 NPs plays a crucial role in the degradation of phenols. There have been many reports on the photocatalytic activity of noble metal doped on BiVO_4 . In a study, it was found that $\text{Cu}-\text{BiVO}_4$ samples degrade phenol under visible-light irradiation, which is synthesized by the HT method and characterized by XRD, N_2 adsorption techniques, SEM, etc. The solution of $\text{Cu}-\text{BiVO}_4$ and phenol-based wastewater was illuminated with a 400 nm cut-off filter under a 400 W metal halide lamp and stirred magnetically till a specific time interval, and the phenol concentration was detected by the UV-vis spectrophotometer [246].

Other organic compounds can also be degraded by nanomaterials like BiVO_4 . One of the critical factors that can affect the sample's performance and visible light activity is its morphology. Hence, tuning the morphology can have a significant impact on degradation kinetics. To do so, H. Jiang et al. [255] prepared different BiVO_4 morphological structures using the alcohol-HT strategy. Oleic acid (OA), oleylamine (OL), and dodecylamine (DA) were used as surfactants, while ethylene glycol

and ethanol played the role of solvent, and NaOH was used as a pH adjuster. The sample code nomenclature BiVO_4 -DA-11 represents BiVO_4 prepared with dodecylamine as a surfactant at pH 11. The SEM images of different combinations are shown in Figs. 14(a)–14(h). Specific observations that can be deduced from the images can be summed up as follows: (i) No surfactant and pH = 1.5 results in irregular structure, (ii) DA surfactant and pH = 1.5 results in porous olive-like morphologies, (iii) for the same DA surfactant, increasing the pH to 7, evolution from olive to shorter rod-like NPs takes place, and when pH reaches 11, spherical shaped particles of $\text{Bi}_4\text{V}_2\text{O}_{11}$ are seen. These observations indicate that for favorable production of monoclinic BiVO_4 , a stronger acidic solution along with DA is required. Also, at pH 1.5, the surfactants were changed to OL, and OA did not change the morphology. Thus, pH plays a more dominant role than surfactants at lower pH values. Meanwhile, porosity and minor structural changes are observed in morphology for the same pH value when changing surfactants.

3.2.4 Potential of BiVO_4 -based photocatalysts for real-world wastewater treatment

Most existing research on industrial wastewater treatment has

Figure 14 SEM images of the (a) BiVO_4 -1.5, (b) BiVO_4 -DA-1.5, (c) BiVO_4 -DA-3, (d) BiVO_4 -DA-7, (e) and (f) BiVO_4 -DA-11, (g) BiVO_4 -OL-1.5, and (h) BiVO_4 -OA-1.5 samples. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [255], © Elsevier B.V. 2011.

primarily focused on a single class of contaminants at very low concentrations, often in ideal laboratory settings. While catalysts may demonstrate good activity under these controlled conditions, real-world scenarios present a more complex challenge. Industrial wastewater typically contains a mixture of various compounds at significantly higher concentrations. Therefore, it is essential to conduct research using actual wastewater generated from industries, focusing on enhancing the scalability of treatment processes to reduce treatment costs effectively.

In a study, textile wastewater was treated using a Ni-doped $\text{PbS}/\text{WO}_3/\text{BiVO}_4$ heterostructure via photocatalysis PC, EC, PEC, and hybrid methods (PC-PEC and EC-PEC). TOC, sulfite, sulfate, chloride, and chromium removal efficiencies were evaluated. The hybrid PC-PEC method achieved the highest pollutant removal efficiency, followed by EC-PEC, PEC, EC, and PC. PEC outperformed PC due to enhanced charge separation and adequate segregation of H_2 and O_2 , preventing recombination and improving hydrogen generation. This study highlights the potential of these methods, particularly hybrid approaches, for efficiently removing diverse pollutants while simultaneously facilitating hydrogen production, making them suitable for scalable industrial wastewater treatment [206].

In a separate study, BiVO_4 synthesized hydrothermally under pH-dependent conditions was employed to degrade industrial pollutants from the leather industry. The photocatalyst exhibited an enhanced degradation rate at increasing pH values (6–8), attributed to improved light absorption, reduced charge carrier recombination, and enhanced photocatalyst stability within this pH range [256]. The $\text{Pt@BiVO}_4/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ photocatalyst, synthesized with 1.5 wt.% platinum at a pH of 8, exhibited exceptional photocatalytic performance, achieving a 93.5% COD removal rate within 3 h during the treatment of real industrial wastewater collected from a local poultry industry in Setiawan, Perak, Malaysia [257].

One of the most promising approaches to advancing industrial wastewater treatment is integrating or enhancing existing systems with photocatalytic technologies. Ahmed Tawfik et al. have highlighted that solar photo-oxidation reactors can be effectively incorporated into conventional wastewater treatment processes, either as pre-treatment or post-treatment units, as an upgrade or an additional component to existing setups. Their review identifies several areas for improvement within conventional and advanced

oxidation processes, emphasizing the potential for further optimization in wastewater remediation strategies [258]. Similarly, a coupling system that combines catalytic wet peroxide oxidation (CWPO) with PC water oxidation using decahedral BiVO_4 crystals has demonstrated remarkable efficiency. This system enables near-complete regeneration of $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ions (~100% selectivity) while simultaneously generating H_2O_2 *in-situ*, thereby minimizing iron sludge formation and H_2O_2 consumption. Furthermore, the coupling approach significantly improves TOC removal, achieving a rate constant over 10 times higher than that of conventional CWPO, offering a highly promising pathway for advanced wastewater remediation [259].

Based on the existing literature, studies focusing on applying BiVO_4 -based photocatalysts for actual wastewater treatment remain limited. There is a critical need for more comprehensive investigations into using BiVO_4 in treating wastewater from various industries, such as municipal sludge, leather, textile, and pharmaceutical sectors. Emphasis should be placed on optimizing and designing photocatalytic reactors that can be seamlessly integrated into existing treatment systems and operate effectively continuously. Furthermore, exploring the stability, reusability, recyclability, and recovery of BiVO_4 -based catalysts after multiple cycles of use is essential. A detailed cost analysis of the synthesis of BiVO_4 compounds is equally important to assess their feasibility for large-scale applications. Addressing these challenges and advancing research in these areas could significantly enhance the potential of BiVO_4 for practical wastewater treatment scenarios.

3.3 Bacterial inactivation

The importance of water for improved quality of human life and health cannot be undermined. Some health issues are caused due to bacteria and other harmful pathogens in contaminated or polluted water. In this context, the exclusion is related to waters that naturally contain organisms without the interference of human activities. Thus, diseases caused by such water are not considered in the pollution disease. Globally, approximately 3 million people die due to diseases caused by contaminated water [260]. According to a survey, approximately one child dies every 21 s due to water-related infection [261]. *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Chlamydomonas pulsatilla* (*C. pulsatilla*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*), etc. are different types of bacteria present in contaminated water. These are

responsible for waterborne diseases like cholera, typhoid, paratyphoid fever, diarrhea, tuberculosis, jaundice, amoebiasis, etc. To protect human lives, the adverse effects of these pathogens should be minimized by sterilizing and inactivating using different techniques.

The photocatalysis mechanism as discussed earlier has various applications such as the degradation of dyes and organic pollutants, while its use in bacterial inactivation is an emerging field of study. In the photocatalytic process, the photocatalysts effectively inactivate the bacteria deemed hazardous for humans and the environment. In addition, the role of solar energy as an abundant and green source makes the entire process promising. The role of different photocatalysts for bacterial inactivation has been studied extensively. Pure and composite forms of other materials are widely used as photocatalysts for this process. Some examples include Ag/g-C₃N₄ [262], graphene/g-C₃N₄ [263], ZnO [264], ZnO-TiO₂ [265], Ag/TiO₂ [266], Bi₂MoO₆/g-C₃N₄ [267, 268], etc. From the literature, TiO₂ is the most stable and active photocatalyst. But there are certain limitations on TiO₂, primarily its more significant response in the UV range [269]. Thus, the lower light response of TiO₂ in the visible region paves the way for designing materials that ensure stability like TiO₂ but have an extended visible light activity.

In this context, BiVO₄ is one of the best photocatalysts for the visible region (Table 6) as it has a narrow band gap of 2.4 eV and demonstrates other advantages like, with benefits such as earth abundance, lower photo-corrosion, high photo-stability, low-toxicity, and cost-effective synthesis. However, the higher rate of the

photogenerated electron-hole pair recombination constraints its usage. Several methods are envisaged to overcome this problem, such as doping with a different metal or non-metal, heterojunction of BiVO₄ with other material, or formation of composites. These approaches can effectively increase the efficiency of BiVO₄ in inactivating the bacteria.

The basic mechanism for bacterial inactivation is explained. When the BiVO₄ is exposed to visible light, charge carriers are generated. The BiVO₄ and photo-generated H⁺, along with its oxidative species like ·OH, H₂O₂, and ·HO₂/·O₂ (ROS), penetrate the cell membrane of bacteria, attack enzymes, and damage the respiratory system. This process leads to the leakage of proteins and nucleic acids, which damages the membrane and leads to the complete destruction of bacteria. The corresponding equations are given below [273]

Table 6 Microbial inactivation by BiVO₄-based materials under visible light

Sr. No.	Material	Morphology	Synthesis method	Bacteria	Efficiency (%)	Time (min)	Major ROS	Ref.
1.	BiVO ₄	Nanoparticle	MWHT	<i>Chlamydomonas Pulsatilla</i>	60	60	O-H	[270]
2.	Gd-BiVO ₄	Sphere and peanut	TM	<i>Enterococcus</i>	41.1	28.8		[271]
3.	Ag-BiVO ₄	Cube	PP	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7.05	180	O ₂ , OH	[272]
	Mo-BiVO ₄		HT	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	4.26	300		
4.	BiVO ₄	Nanoparticle	MWHT	<i>Chlamydomonas Pulsatilla</i>	60	60	H ⁺ , OH	[273]
	Ni-BiVO ₄	Rod and sheet	MWH	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	89	300		
	BiVO ₄	Nanoparticle	MWHT	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	70	300		
	Ni-BiVO ₄	Sheet	MWHT	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	92	300		
5.	BiVO ₄	Nanoparticle	MWHT	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	70	300	O ₂ , -OH	[274]
	Ni-BiVO ₄	Rod	MWHT	<i>Chlamydomonas Pulsatilla</i>	70	60		
6.	CuO _x -Mo/BiVO ₄	Quasi-spherical	WI	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	100	120	O ₂ , -OH	[275]
				<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	100	120		
7.	Nb-BiVO ₄	Hierarchical	DBM	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	43	60	O ₂ , -OH	[276]
8.	GO-BiVO ₄	Nanoparticle	SG	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	89	60	O ₂ , -OH	[277]
9.	BiVO ₄ /g-C ₃ N ₄	Nano rod	PD/HM	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	66.6	60	h ⁺ , ·O ₂	[278]
	BiVO ₄ /Ag/g-C ₃ N ₄	Nano rod	PD/HM	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	99.9	60		
10.	AgI/ BiVO ₄	Spherical	HT	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	99.99	30	·O ₂ , h ⁺	[279]
	BiVO ₄	Spherical	HT	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	77	30		
				<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	99.55	300		
11.	InVO ₄ / BiVO ₄	Cherimoya	HT	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	96	300	·OH, O ₂ ⁻	[280]
				<i>Escherichia coli</i>	99.54	300		
12.	AgVO ₃ /BiVO ₄	Micro-block	HT	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	99.99	30	O ₂ ⁻ , h ⁺	[281]

Zheng yao Qu et al. synthesized BiVO_4 at different pH values ranging from 5 to 13 without the capping agent. The XRD of samples prepared at different pH is shown in Fig. 15(a). From XRD, we can conclude that an increase in pH from 1 to 5 gradually increases the intensity of peaks at $2\theta = 18.5^\circ$ and 27.5° , while further growth in the pH, lowers the corresponding intensities. Also, the pH 5 prepared sample had the highest degree of match with the monoclinic BiVO_4 . The pH condition highly affected the morphology of synthesized materials. It was found that a sheet-like structure was obtained in acidic conditions, while branched morphology was seen in a basic medium, as shown in Figs. 15(b)–15(g) and 15(l). Also, the sample prepared at pH 5 had the highest photocatalytic activity and the best response for bacterial inactivation. The FE-SEM images of *E. Coli* before and after treatment with BiVO_4 and its effect on the surface change are seen in Figs. 15(h)–15(k). A basic mechanism for bacterial inactivation was discussed based on the FE-SEM analysis. The outer membrane of *E. coli* has a composition of peptidoglycan, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), and periplasm, while the inner membrane consists of protein and phospholipid chains. So, electrons and holes are generated when the light is incident on BiVO_4 , which reacts with LPS molecules to relax them. This process damages the membrane, which inactivates the *E. coli* bacteria [282].

Rishabh Sharma et al. [273] synthesized monoclinic BiVO_4 nanostructures using the HT method. In this study, they observed that the inactivation of *E. coli* increased with increasing concentrations of BiVO_4 . Here, NPs of BiVO_4 penetrate through the cell wall to damage enzymes and reduce bacterial growth. The reduction in the development of bacteria in 2 h was about 80% for 20 ppm BiVO_4 . When 80 ppm BiVO_4 was used, the complete inactivation occurred within 2 h. Velu Manikandan et al. [275] synthesized, for the first time, visible light active CuO_x -loaded Mo- BiVO_4 photocatalysts using the wet impregnation method for improved photocatalytic inactivation of *S. aureus* and *E. Coli*. The increase in the inactivation performance was attributed to the synergistic effect of Mo doping and Cu^{2+} ions in CuO_x . These ions

worked as an electron entrapment site for the Mo- BiVO_4 surface and boosted the rapid separation and transfer of the photogenerated electron-hole pair required for the formation of ROS. The best result was demonstrated by 2 wt.% CuO_x -loaded Mo- BiVO_4 for the inactivation of *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, and 98% of these bacteria were inactivated in 120 min.

Similarly, Zhenbo Xiang and co-workers [279] synthesized pure AgI, BiVO_4 , and AgI/ BiVO_4 , by using the HT method. 20% AgI/ BiVO_4 exhibited the highest performance, and complete inactivation of *P. aeruginosa* took place within 30 min, while high activity was retained for five cycles. The composite material in the study was AgI. The choice of AgI is due to the excellent results of Ag-based photocatalyst in the bacterial inactivity while its bandgap of approximately 2.8 eV favors the improved performance. It even improves visible light absorption capability by acting as a sensitizer. The limitation of using pure AgI is due to its instability under illumination in the pure form. Therefore, AgI is coupled with stable semiconductor BiVO_4 to enhance photocatalytic activity. The photogenerated electrons react with liquefied oxygen in the surroundings to generate $\cdot\text{O}_2$ radicals. The formed O_2 , holes, etc. free radicals vandalize the bacterial cell wall, leading to the leakage of the intracellular materials and finally destroying the bacteria.

X. Zeng et al. [278] developed a ternary Z-scheme $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ composite synthesized via photodeposition and HT method for the inactivation of bacteria *E. Coli*. Both the materials, i.e. BiVO_4 and g- C_3N_4 , show good photocatalytic activity. They also have some restrictions because of Coulombic forces between negatively charged electrons and holes, such as the high charge carrier recombination rate of photogenerated electron-hole pairs, which leads to lower photocatalytic disinfection. Thus, both photocatalysts are composited together to form $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Ag}/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$, and the resulting material overcomes the problem mentioned above and shows excellent performance compared to other samples. As discussed earlier, Ag is an effective photocatalyst and, as a sensitizer, in this case, acts as an electron mediator for improving performance in this Z-scheme-styled composite.

Also, doping with transition metals like Ni was studied by C. Regmi and co-workers [274]. They synthesized BiVO_4 and Ni-doped BiVO_4 photocatalysts and found that the Ni-doped

Figure 15 (a) XRD patterns of the BiVO_4 samples prepared at different hydrothermal pH values. Morphology of BiVO_4 prepared under (b) pH = 1, (c) pH = 3, (d) pH = 5, (e) pH = 7, (f) pH = 9, (g) pH = 11, and (l) pH = 13. FESEM images with a different magnification of bacteria before ((h) and (i)) and after ((j) and (k)) treatment of BiVO_4 with the illumination of visible light. The cells in images ((i) and (k)) were derived separately from images ((h) and (j)) with higher magnification. Reproduced with permission with Ref. [282], © Qu, Z. Y. et al. 2016.

vanadium side showed the most stable composition of BiVO_4 due to the build-up of in-gap energy states and oxygen vacancies. These acted as electron-trapping sites, thereby reducing the migration time and improving the recombination efficiency of electron-hole pairs. In presence of visible light irradiation, the optimized sample 1% Ni- BiVO_4 deactivates *E. coli* 92% in 5 h (Figs. 16(a)–16(d)), while for *C. pulsatilla*, 70% of the bacteria inactivate in 60 min (Figs. 16(h)–16(j)). Also, Figs. 16(e)–16(g) show the SEM images of BiVO_4 (in dark), BiVO_4 (in light), and Ni- BiVO_4 (in light) treated bacteria *E. coli* and *C. pulsatilla*, respectively. The bandgap of BiVO_4 , i.e., 2.30 eV, gets lowered by 0.06 and 0.05 eV for the doped sample for both the spin-majority and spin-minority states, respectively. This deduction of the bandgap is compatible with the practical remarks. The atom projected that the stronger DOS in-gap state would emerge just above the Fermi level, otherwise missing in the pure BiVO_4 . This in-gap state most probably promotes successive photoexcitation of electrons in the visible range. Hence, the separation and diffusion rates jointly provide better photocatalytic, antibacterial, and anti-algal activity of the Ni-doped BiVO_4 .

From the above-mentioned experimental ideas and literature, we attempt to conclude that to improve the bacterial inactivation activity of BiVO_4 , strategies like heterojunction or doping of material with some other semiconductor, metal, etc., are beneficial for photocatalytic and antibacterial performances. Some difficulties for long-term photocatalytic stability and using non-hazardous chemicals during the synthesis process must be addressed. Also, the period of inactivation of bacteria must be reduced to the maximum extent possible. More studies are focused on the inactivation of a

few types of bacteria, like *E. coli*, but the work can also be extended to other kinds of bacteria. This can be done using the same material or any composition with the appropriate material, and thus, it will deepen our understanding of this field.

3.4 BiVO_4 for photocatalytic fuel production

3.4.1 BiVO_4 for CO_2 reduction

CO_2 is a small but essential component of the atmosphere. Natural processes such as volcanic eruptions, deforestation, land-use changes due to human activities, and the burning of fossil fuels release CO_2 into the atmosphere. Reports from the Global Climate Change and Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) have estimated that the atmospheric CO_2 content will reach up to 590 ppm by the year 2100, which will result in a rising global average temperature of 1.9 °C and would eventually result in scary situations like sea level rise, climate change, etc. [283]. Hence, to avoid conditions like global warming and catastrophic consequences, it is necessary to develop a sustainable solution for converting CO_2 into beneficial compounds in an hour. Among the various emerging strategies, a successful and promising way that addresses global warming as well as satisfies the demand for renewable fuel is the photocatalytic conversion of CO_2 with H_2O into valuable chemicals like hydrocarbon fuels [284].

However, achieving precise control over the selective production of specific target fuels, categorized into C_1 products (e.g., CO , CH_4 , CH_3OH , and HCOOH) and C_2/C_2+ products (e.g., C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , C_3H_6 , and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$), remains a formidable challenge due to the inherent complexity of multi-electron and proton-coupled electron

Figure 16 Photographs of bacterial colonies formed by *E. coli*; (a) control; (b) BiVO_4 (dark); (c) BiVO_4 ; (d) BiVO_4 -Ni, irradiation to visible light; and FE-SEM images showing *E. coli* cell damage on irradiation to the visible light; (e) control; (f) BiVO_4 ; (g) BiVO_4 -Ni-1. FE-SEM images of *Chlamydomonas pulsatilla* treated with (h) control, (i) BiVO_4 , (j) BiVO_4 -Ni-1 in the presence of visible light for 60 min. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [274], © Elsevier B.V. 2017.

transfer (PCET) processes [285]. Notably, H₂ evolution via the HER competes directly with CO₂ reduction within a similar potential range, further complicating the reaction selectivity [286]. The mechanism, thermodynamics, and kinetics of CO₂ reduction, as well as its pathways and key processes, are significantly influenced by factors such as the electronic band structure of the photocatalyst and the Gibbs free energy supplied through light irradiation [287]. Karamian and Sharifnia proposed a general mechanism for PC CO₂ reduction (Fig. 17), which involves the formation of oxidizing agents, the oxidation of reducing species, and the subsequent reduction of CO₂ by various reductants [288].

Several advanced strategies have been proposed to overcome these challenges and regulate electron transfer processes precisely. These include the development of highly selective catalysts, such as materials with engineered defects, and applying photocatalyst modulation techniques, such as light intensity tuning, bandgap engineering via doping or co-doping, cocatalyst deposition, defect generation, and facet engineering. These approaches collectively enhance CO₂ adsorption, activation, and stabilization of reaction intermediates [289]. Furthermore, nanostructured photocatalysts with tailored morphologies can improve product selectivity by providing particular active sites. Optimizing the electrolyte composition, for instance, using ionic liquids or alkali metal cations, plays a crucial role in stabilizing intermediates and regulating proton availability [290]. Additionally, the careful control of applied overpotentials is critical; lower potentials favor single-electron processes, leading to the formation of hydrocarbons such as CH₄ and C₂H₄ [291].

Till now, the most promising and notably visible-light-driven (VLD) metal oxides and sulfides, such as Bi₂WO₆ [292], BiVO₄ [21], WO₃ [293], CdS [294], etc., were identified, which help to reduce CO₂. For efficient CO₂ reduction and sufficient solar-to-fuel (STF) conversion, various strategies, such as nano structuring, heterojunction formation, Z-scheme constructing, etc., have been investigated under visible light irradiation.

In every photocatalytic activity, valence band structure, visible light absorption ability, and efficiency determine the usefulness of a particular semiconductor. Under visible-light irradiation, the VB electrons of the selected catalyst can be excited up, resulting in charge transfer and separation processes, which are arbitrated by

either the double-charge transfer mode or the Z-scheme transfer mechanism [104]. From the experimental results, it is confirmed that the main active species (radicals) responsible for the degradation of various textile, pharmaceutical, and organic types of dyes are e⁻, OH[·], h⁺, and O₂^{-·} [295].

The main factors affecting the photocatalytic CO₂ conversion using semiconductor NPs are particle size, morphology, valence states, etc. Precautions are to be taken while loading the cocatalyst because an increase in the cocatalyst loading can lead to the deterioration of photocatalytic activity. The excessive co-catalyst can block the incident radiative light, reduce the surface active sites, and form larger particles and non-uniform dispersion, leading to reduced catalytic activity [296]. The reactions for the formation of organic compounds such as formic acid, formaldehyde, methanol, and methane are associated by 2-, 4-, 6-, and 8-electron transfers, respectively, which are described as follows

Different research groups have strategically worked to use BiVO₄ for CO₂ reduction, and there has been an increasing interest in this field in the past few years. Monoclinic BiVO₄ molecules are well matched for water oxidation reactions coupled with hydrogen and CO₂ reduction evolution. The photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ using BiVO₄ can lead to the formation of ethanol and methanol under visible or UV light radiation [295].

CO₂ photoreduction by BiVO₄ consequently requires bases like NaOH in aqueous solutions. In the process, BiVO₄ molecules are transformed into Bi₂O_{4-x} nanoparticles and are deposited on the catalyst's surface. The deposited NPs appeared to be very dense compared to the bulk of BiVO₄. Because of that, the catalyst becomes deactivated and subsequently decreases the rate of CO₂ reduction activity. The electron-rich deposits on the surface can be removed by heating the catalyst to 1500 °C. It also reactivated the

Figure 17 The proposed reaction mechanism of aqueous phase photocatalysis of CO₂ + H₂O and the potentials required for different reactions. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [288], © Elsevier Ltd. 2016.

catalyst by drawing vanadium density from the inner BiVO_4 . A fraction of the original catalyst may degrade or be depleted after each cycle of photoreduction and recovery. The primary potential products in the CO_2 reduction process include methanol, formate, and formaldehyde [297].

To understand the role of phase, Liu et al. prepared BiVO_4 photocatalysts using the microwave-assisted HT method and compared the catalytic reduction of CO_2 to ethanol effects of two phases, i.e., tetragonal and monoclinic. The experiments demonstrated that monoclinic showed superior reduction properties compared to the tetragonal phase. A plausible explanation for the observed effect is the stronger asymmetry in the local environment of Bi^{3+} ion for the monoclinic phase compared to the tetragonal phase. This results in the robust lone pair character of the Bi^{3+} ion that improved the tendency to form the Bi–O bond with CO_3^{2-} and hence the transfer of photogenerated electrons and the catalytic activity [21]. The phase-dependent strategy was used by J. Mao et al. [22] to prepare monoclinic BiVO_4 with a slight change during the testing. The earlier report used water as the solvent during the testing process, but this group showed that NaOH solution should be added to water to increase the yield of methanol considerably. The NaOH concentration also affects the yield of methanol; for zero concentration of NaOH, the obtained yield was 0.6 mol, which improved 50 times for 1 M NaOH, keeping all the experimental conditions the same. The caustic solution provides more significant OH^- ions that serve as strong hole-scavengers compared to water and thus can dissolve more CO_2 . It is often observed that using only BiVO_4 as a photocatalyst gives lower yield values than the standard benchmark materials. Different strategies can be used to enhance the values, like doping with other elements or heterojunction. The composite can be obtained with varying materials like metal oxides, carbon-based materials, etc. One of the emerging carbon-based materials, rGO, was used by Wang and co-workers to synthesize BiVO_4/rGO nanocomposites, and a comparative study was carried out (Figs. 18(a)–18(f)). The composite showed an improvement of

50.1% in photo-reduction efficiency and increased ethanol yield by 1.4 times compared to pure BiVO_4 . The rGO provides and facilitates an easy pathway for interfacial charge transfer of photo-generated electrons and, thus, higher performance [298]. Other areas of interest, like designing the assembly of unassisted devices for CO_2 -to-fuel conversion and solar-integrated tandem devices that are highly selective and efficient, remain a challenge [299].

3.4.2 N_2 fixation

N_2 is one of the inert chemical species in nature with high $\text{N}\equiv\text{N}$ dissociation energy ($941 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). The production of N_2 -based fertilizers is a highly energy-intensive process, and it accounts for about 2% of global energy consumption [300]. N_2 reduction is an exothermal process that produces ammonia in the Haber–Bosch process under high temperature and high-pressure conditions. This process is energy-consuming and causes notable environmental issues. N_2 fixation by photocatalysis is an emerging technique to accomplish the green production of ammonia. This process is environmentally friendly and cost-effective. In detail, water serves as the hydrogen source in photocatalytic N_2 fixation, rather than natural gas [301]. Also, this process can be completed under ambient conditions. This process is far satisfactory because of high activation energy barriers, inefficient separation of photogenerated carriers, and cleavage of $\text{N}\equiv\text{N}$. Photocatalytic N_2 reduction is simple to perform and does not require an external source of electricity. N_2 reduction over heterogeneous catalysis involves: 1) chemisorption of N_2 and H_2 on the surface of catalysts, 2) reductive addition of hydrogen atom and association and dissociation of N_2 , and 3) ammonia desorption from the catalyst surface. Until now, N_2 reduction on a heterogenous catalyst to form ammonia is achieved by two N_2 reduction pathways-dissociative and associative [302–304]. Once photocatalysis attains an adequate level of solar-to-chemical conversion efficiency, it has the potential to transform energy utilization and fertilizer manufacturing on a large scale. Unlike CO_2 reduction, the N_2 molecule features nonpolar bonds, making the precise design of catalytic sites, such as heteroatomic

Figure 18 TEM image of (a) graphite oxide, (b) RGO, (c) BiVO_4 particles, and (d) $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{RGO-40}$ composites. (e) EIS of BiVO_4 and $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{RGO-40}$ nanocomposites. (f) The ethanol yield with respect to the time. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [298], © Elsevier Inc. 2015.

configurations, crucial for enhanced performance. Notably, the characterization and analysis of intermediates formed during N₂ reduction are comparatively simpler than those in CO₂ reduction. This simplicity provides an opportunity for deeper exploration into the underlying reaction pathways [305].

The N₂ fixation mechanism consists of nitrogen oxidation reaction (NOR) and NRR (nitrogen reduction reaction) where oxidation and reduction take place simultaneously. The basic NRR involves multiple steps as follows: Firstly, when visible light is incident on photocatalyst, photoexcited electron-hole pair gets generated. Here, excited holes react with water molecules to give H⁺ and O₂. Then, the excited electrons reduce N₂ to give the product NH₃ [306]. The overall equation is mentioned below

Step-I

Step-II

Overall

Considering the advantages of BiVO₄ as discussed in earlier sections, and from Table 7, we can see that various strategies and material designs have emerged to justify the critical role of BiVO₄ in the photocatalytic N₂ fixation mechanism. Yajie Bai et al. demonstrated the usefulness of p-BiVO₄ in PEC NRR. Notably, at a

significantly less potential -0.1 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M Li₂SO₄ solution, p-BiVO₄ photocathode displayed remarkable performance of 11.6 × 10⁻⁸ mol·h⁻¹·cm⁻² and Faradaic efficiency (16.2%). The results from the isotope tracing tests showed that the NH₃ was totally produced from N₂ PEC NRR. Additionally, the DFT results showed that the V site functions as a crucial activation site for the N-N triple bond and supports the idea that the adsorption of N₂ onto *N₂ is the reaction's rate-limiting phase [25].

Through *in-situ* photocatalytic NRR (pNRR) on a single crystal of BiVO₄, G. Zhang and co-workers [317] demonstrated that the oxygen vacancy (OV)-V⁴⁺/V⁵⁺ on (040) facet was a specific active site for pNRR. The chemisorption of N₂ by V⁴⁺, the electron transfer activity of V⁵⁺, and the photogenerated electrons imprisoned in OVs acted as a catalyst for the ammonia synthesis. The influence of facet ratio growth was due to only V⁵⁺, which could not produce the initial step of chemisorption of N₂. Thus, by altering active sites on the (040) facet, NRR performance was linearly boosted. With an increase in the (040)/(110) facet ratio, the most significant activity of 103.4 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹ without using a sacrificial reagent was obtained.

Wang et al. [313] used alcohol as a reducing solvent to create mulberry-like BiVO₄ with OVs. Results from Raman, EPR, and XPS demonstrated that OVs were successfully introduced. According to tests, the CB, which has the capacity for photocatalytic N₂ fixation, differs from the defect energy level produced by oxygen vacancies by 0.20 eV. Low-energy light is better utilized in the synthesized material due to the presence of OVs. The electrons accumulated on the CB of the OVs-BiVO₄ under optical irradiation can be moved to the defect level to stop carriers from recombining. A 300 W Xe-lamp produced Ag-OVs-BiVO₄ to increase the OV-catalytic BiVO₄ firmly to the surface of OVs-BiVO₄, producing a potent LSPR action. The LSPR effect expands the visible light absorption range. The excited electrons on the CB of the OVs-BiVO₄ can also be transported to Ag to activate N₂, which lowers

Table 7 N₂ fixation using BiVO₄-based compounds under visible light irradiation

Sr. No.	Material	Synthesis method	Product	Yield rate	Light source	Ref.
1.	BiVO ₄ /PANI	ED	NH ₃	0.93 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²	300 W Xe	[307]
	CoFeMnO/BiVO ₄			17.82 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²		
	CoFeO/BiVO ₄			10.72 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²		
	CoFeCuO/BiVO ₄			12.05 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²		
2.	CoFeNiO/BiVO ₄	HT	NH ₃	17.07 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²	300 W Xe	[308]
	CoFeMnNiO/BiVO ₄			7.96 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²		
	CoFeNiCuO/BiVO ₄			7.37 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²		
	CoFeMnCuO/BiVO ₄			5.95 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²		
	CoFeMnNiCuO/BiVO ₄			7.69 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²		
3.	BiVO ₄ /MnCO ₃ /C	HT	NH ₃	2.426 mmol·m ⁻² ·h ⁻¹	300 W Xe	[309]
4.	BiVO ₄ /MXene	HT	NH ₃	27.25 μg·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²	300 W Xe	[310]
5.	BiVO ₄	HT	NH ₃	11.6 × 10 ⁻⁸ mol·h ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻²	300 W Xe	[25]
6.	BiVO ₄	WC	NH ₄ ⁺	15.5 μmol·g ⁻¹ ·L ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹	300 W Xe	[311]
7.	3% Au-BiVO ₄	PD	NH ₄ ⁺	0.419 mg·L ⁻¹	500 W Xe	[312]
8.	OVs-BiVO ₄	PD	NH ₃	32.4 μmol·g ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹	300 W Xe (λ > 420 nm)	[313]
	5%Ag-OVs-BiVO ₄			48 μmol·g ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹		
9.	BiVO ₄ /rGO	ST	NO ₃ ⁻	1.45 mg·h ⁻¹ ·g ⁻¹	300 W Xe (λ > 420 nm)	[314]
10.	Bi/BiVO ₄	PD	NH ₄ ⁺	167.74 μmol·g ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹	300 W Xe	[315]
11.	Ru/BiVO ₄	HT	NH ₃	16.57 μmol·g ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹	300 W Xe	[316]

Figure 19 (a) The synthesis scheme, (b) TEM, (c) HRTEM images, (d) HAADF-STEM image of the BG-1 sample. (e) Comparison of photocatalytic N_2 oxidation performance of different samples. (f) Time course of photocatalytic NO_3^- production over the BG-1 sample. (g) Wavelength-dependent apparent QE under monochromatic light irradiation and the light absorption spectrum of the BG-1 sample. (h) Schematic of photocatalytic N_2 oxidation to nitrates over the BiVO_4/rGO composite. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [314], © The Royal Society of Chemistry 2022.

carrier recombination. This overall all charge transfer process is used for photocatalytic N_2 fixation.

The interaction of 2D materials with BiVO_4 can also be used to deepen our understanding of the role and interaction of such a composite for improved performance. Shao et al. [314] produced a thin nanocomposite of rGO and BiVO_4 nano sheets photocatalyst for N_2 oxidation into nitrate (Fig. 19(a)). The unique 2D/2D heterostructure with rGO (Figs. 19(b)–19(d)) has two essential advantages: Firstly it hastens the separation and transmission of photogenerated charge carrier via close contact with an ultrathin BiVO_4 nanosheet. Secondly, when rGO is used, from theoretical modeling, rGO can not only speed up the adsorption and activation of N_2 molecules but also lower the free energy of reaction required to generate NO, which promotes the NOR process. The BG (BiVO_4/rGO)-1 sample showed a high NO_3^- yield rate of $1.45 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (Figs. 19(e) and 19(f)), and an apparent QE shows 64% at 420 nm (Fig. 19(g)). It is one of the most highly active

photocatalysts for nitrate synthesis and the corresponding schematic is shown in Fig. 19(h). This research provides a novel use of BiVO_4 for the photocatalytic oxidation of N_2 to nitrates and indicates a potential mechanism that may aid in the comprehension of the photocatalytic NOR process in other systems. Demei Zhang and co-workers [310] used the HT method to synthesize the $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MXene}$ hybrid. The *in-situ* growth significantly boosted NRR efficiency. The Faraday efficiency reaches up to 17.54% at 0.8 V with an NH_3 yield of $27.25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ relative to RHE. According to the mechanism predictions, the increased light absorption range and heterojunction creation are believed to improve photogenerated charge carriers' separation and charge transfer efficiency, which enhanced the PEC catalytic ability. $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MXene}$ composites, synthesized by Demei Zhang and colleagues via an HT method, demonstrated efficient heterojunction formation through *in-situ* BiVO_4 on 2D MXene growth. Under PEC conditions, the optimized composite achieved

an NH_3 yield of $27.25 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and a Faradaic efficiency of 17.54% at -0.8 V vs. RHE, outperforming many advanced NRR photoelectrocatalysts. UV-vis analysis revealed a narrowed bandgap (1.84 eV) compared to pure BiVO_4 (2.22 eV), facilitating broader visible light absorption. The improved PEC performance was attributed to enhanced light harvesting, prolonged photogenerated electron lifespan, and effective charge separation via heterojunction formation [310]. A $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{MoS}_2$ S-scheme heterojunction, enriched with sulfur vacancies in MoS_2 nanosheets, was developed for PC N_2 fixation. Sulfur vacancies promoted N_2 adsorption and activation, while the S-scheme heterojunction enhanced charge separation and water oxidation efficiency. The system achieved an NH_3 production rate of $132.8 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ using H_2O as a proton source, nearly seven times higher than pure MoS_2 . These results highlight the critical role of sulfur vacancies in N_2 activation and the importance of S-scheme heterojunctions in optimizing charge carrier dynamics [318].

Yunliang Liu et al. [319] presented a simple procedure for synthesizing a heterojunction interface-rich BiVO_4/TNT catalyst. In addition to providing a surface for N_2 adsorption, BiVO_4 composite on the TNT surface could produce more OVs and heterojunction, as well as improved electron transfers and NRR catalytic activity. In $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ electrolyte solution, the BiVO_4/TNT had a greater ammonia production. This research could stimulate the rational design of TiO_2 -based composite catalysts with heterojunction arrangement and abundant OVs with yield $8.54 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and very high Faradic efficiency of 7.70% at -0.8 V vs. RHE in $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution. Yajie Bai et al. [307] used HT and ED techniques to create a $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{PANI}$ Z-scheme heterojunction successfully. The separation and transfer of photogenerated charge carriers were expedited due to the staggered band structure and flawless interface, producing exceptional PEC NRR performance. The $\text{BiVO}_4/\text{PANI}$ Z-scheme heterojunction performed admirably in terms of PEC NRR compared to BiVO_4 . High stability and selectivity were also exhibited, with no N_2H_4 being found. By creating a Z-scheme heterojunction, this work has achieved effective NRR performance and offers an appealing technique for creating further effective catalysts. F. Wang and co-researchers [308] observed that entropy influences the degree of catalytic reaction; they proposed a novel method for HT synthesis of $\text{A-M}_x\text{O}_y/\text{BiVO}_4$ and effectively demonstrated that the addition of amorphous ternary $\text{A-M}_x\text{O}_y(\text{CoFeMnO})$ results in the achievement of optimal PEC- NO_3^- reduction reaction performance by altering the composition of elements. Due to the abundance of active sites available, the adsorption/activation of NO_3^- is enhanced by incorporating metastable amorphous CoFeMnO with p-BiVO_4 . $\text{CoFeMnO}/\text{BiVO}_4$'s yield rate was nearly twice as high as p-BiVO_4 's, at about $17.82 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (-0.1 V vs. RHE). As an affordable photocatalyst for the visible-light active photo fixation of N_2 , an Au-modified BiVO_4 photocatalyst was successfully created by G. X and S. Meirong [312]. Both the carrier separation and the production of many hot electrons could be accelerated by the plasmonic Au NPs, improving the performance. The strong triple bonds of N_2 molecules might be broken by the synergistic impact of the two events mentioned above, resulting in the formation of NH_4^+ . The Au loading levels could be changed to improve Au/BiVO_4 performance. The 3% Au/BiVO_4 photocatalyst exhibited an outstanding performance for N_2 fixation with a significant NH_4^+ evolution rate ($0.419 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and high stability. Monoclinic BiVO_4 was created by H. Shi and the team using the HT process [320].

They added ZnSe NP on BiVO_4 to form a composite of $\text{ZnSe}/\text{BiVO}_4$. The $\text{ZnSe}/\text{BiVO}_4$ composite, which improved light absorption and charge separation efficiency, increased performance by up to 97.6% for ammonia production. Honghao Chu and the team [311] produced different exposed facets BiVO_4 {010} and {110}. They showed for the first time the application of BiVO_4 {010} and {110} facets for N_2 fixation. This anisotropic facet {010} of BiVO_4 enhanced the charge separation between electrons and holes. The BiVO_4 {010} showed better performance for N_2 fixation compared with BiVO_4 {110} due to more significant charge separation between electron and hole and a greater number of OVs available on this BiVO_4 {010}.

Thus, the photocatalytic method of N_2 fixation by a BiVO_4 -based catalyst is promising among different existing methods. Specific strategies discussed above, like creating oxygen vacancy, doping with other materials, building heterojunction with relevant material, etc., can considerably boost performance. The approach can be extended to other N_2 fixation mechanisms like nitrates, nitrites, etc. production.

3.5 Strategies to improve stability of BiVO_4 -based materials

BiVO_4 is a promising photoanode material for PEC water splitting; however, its long-term stability in alkaline conditions remains a critical challenge, limiting its practical applicability. Incorporating composite materials can significantly enhance the stability of photoelectrodes in PEC water-splitting systems, effectively addressing the limitations of bare BiVO_4 .

Bin Gao et al. addressed this issue by employing a protective coating of poly(p-phenylene pyromellitimide) (PPPI) on the BiVO_4 surface. This polymeric layer effectively enhances the stability and PEC performance of BiVO_4 by facilitating charge carrier dynamics. The application of PPPI on BiVO_4 significantly boosted PEC activity, achieving 2.5 times higher efficiency than uncoated BiVO_4 . This enhancement resulted from better hole transfer to the surface and more effective charge separation at the interface. Notably, the photocurrent retention exceeded 70% even after six hours of operation under strongly alkaline conditions, demonstrating the effectiveness of the protective layer in preserving the photoanode's functionality [321].

In another work, the pristine BiVO_4 electrode exhibits pronounced instability, with a 50% decay in photocurrent over 2 h of operation due to poor charge separation efficiency and photocorrosion. In contrast, the $\text{FTO}/\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe-Pi}$ composite electrode, fabricated using SILAR, demonstrates negligible photocurrent decay under identical conditions while achieving a significantly higher photocurrent density ($J_{\text{sc}} \approx 2.28 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE). This improvement highlights the Fe-Pi cocatalyst's role in mitigating photocorrosion and facilitating efficient charge transfer [322]. Similarly, the $\text{FTO}/\text{BiVO}_4/\text{Fe}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{OOH}$ composite electrode exhibits remarkable stability enhancements. While the bare BiVO_4 electrode undergoes complete photocurrent decay within 3 h, the addition of the $\text{Fe}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{OOH}$ cocatalyst via a pH-modulated immersion method results in negligible decay over the same period, with a significantly increased photocurrent density ($J_{\text{sc}} \approx 5.8 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE). This enhanced stability is attributed to the cocatalyst's ability to suppress surface recombination, improve charge separation, and protect the BiVO_4 surface from oxidative degradation [323]. Additionally, the $\text{FTO}/\text{WCoFe}/\text{BiVO}_4$ oxyhydroxide composite electrode,

synthesized through a solvothermal process, achieves excellent stability with negligible decay over 2 h of operation. This is in stark contrast to the instability of bare BiVO_4 , with the composite electrode maintaining a stable photocurrent density ($J_{sc} \approx 4.35 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE) due to the oxyhydroxide layer's protective and catalytic properties. The negligible decay observed in these composite systems underscores the transformative impact of cocatalyst engineering in mitigating the intrinsic limitations of BiVO_4 , ensuring sustained performance, and enhancing their viability for long-term PEC water-splitting applications [324]. Rui-Ting Gao et al. developed an *in-situ* approach to enhance the stability and performance of BiVO_4 in neutral electrolyte conditions by incorporating Ni and B species. Ni acts as catalytic active sites to improve the OER, while borate ions substitute vanadium in BiVO_4 , enhancing the material's photochemical properties. The dissolution of vanadium from BiVO_4 is a critical issue that diminishes surface water oxidation efficiency and directly impacts the device's operational lifetime. Borate ions were employed to address this challenge, as these ions substitute either V^{5+} or Bi^{3+} within the BiVO_4 lattice, effectively stabilizing the structure. By exposing BiVO_4 to a NaB electrolyte saturated with V^{5+} or Bi^{3+} , the dissolution of these elements was inhibited, thereby enhancing the material's stability and prolonging its functional lifetime. The overall effect of Ni and B in the NiB/BiVO_4 facilitates efficient charge separation and transfer, suppressing photo-corrosion and improving overall stability. This novel design achieved long-term stability of up to 600 h, demonstrating excellent durability. The NiB/BiVO_4 exhibited a remarkable photocurrent density of $6.0 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE, highlighting its potential for scalable PEC applications [325]. Yongcai Qiu and collaborators synthesized BiVO_4 hitherto and investigated its carrier diffusion length, a key limiting factor affecting film thickness and light absorption efficiency. To address this challenge, the team developed a nanostructured Mo-doped BiVO_4 (Mo:BiVO_4) with a non-porous, cone-like morphology. The nanocone structure, approximately 600 nm in height, significantly improved charge transport and light harvesting capabilities. This modification resulted in an enhanced photocurrent density of $6.05 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, surpassing that of unmodified Mo:BiVO_4 . The nanocone structure ensures efficient charge transport, even with a thick Mo:BiVO_4 layer, due to the reduced carrier diffusion length enabled by the conductive nature of the nanocone. The overall device stability was tested for 10 h, showing only a 5.8% decay in performance, indicating excellent stability. This minimal decay highlights the robustness of the system and its potential for long-term operation [5]. The way that BiVO_4 photoanodes dissolve in borate, phosphate, and citrate electrolytes varies greatly. Bi and V dissolve simultaneously in borate, suggesting homogenous deterioration, whereas they dissolve at different potentials in phosphate, causing preferential degradation of the V-rich region and rapid corrosion. As a hole scavenger, citrate lessens oxidative damage, protecting the integrity of the surface and postponing photocorrosion. Because photocurrent measurements alone cannot accurately reflect deterioration—particularly in thicker films—in *operando* dissolution monitoring provides a more accurate method for assessing photostability. Each electrolyte has a unique surface chemistry and shape, with citrate providing protection, phosphate generating localized corrosion and borate exhibiting uniform deterioration. Strategies to improve stability should shield V-rich areas from exposure, especially in phosphate systems, and use electrolytes that scavenge holes, such as citrate, to reduce oxidative stress. These realizations enhance BiVO_4 's resilience in PEC water splitting [326]. Dong Ki Lee et al. studied the photodegradation of

BiVO_4 and proposed a strategy to mitigate this issue. They used a V^{3+} saturated electrolyte, which effectively inhibited the photooxidation-coupled dissolution of V^{5+} , preventing the anodic photo corrosion of BiVO_4 . This approach helps to stabilize the BiVO_4 photoanode by reducing the dissolution of V-rich regions, thereby improving its long-term performance in PEC water splitting [327].

The stability of BiVO_4 photoelectrodes in PEC water splitting is significantly enhanced through cocatalyst integration, dopant incorporation, and electrolyte optimization. Cocatalysts such as Fe-Pi, $\text{Fe}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{OOH}$, and WCoFe oxyhydroxide mitigate photocorrosion, suppress surface recombination, and facilitate efficient charge transfer, ensuring prolonged operational stability. The incorporation of Ni and borate species stabilizes the BiVO_4 lattice by inhibiting vanadium dissolution, achieving extended durability of up to 600 h with improved photocurrent density. Nanostructured Mo-doped BiVO_4 with a cone-like morphology enhances charge carrier transport and light absorption, reducing performance degradation over time. Electrolyte engineering is crucial in photostability, with citrate as a hole scavenger to minimize oxidative damage. In contrast, V^{3+} saturated electrolytes prevent preferential vanadium leaching, improving long-term PEC performance.

4 Conclusion and future perspectives

This review highlights the immense potential of BiVO_4 -based photocatalysts for a diverse range of applications, particularly in visible-light-driven processes. By systematically discussing the intrinsic properties of BiVO_4 —such as its crystal structure and electronic and optical characteristics—alongside experimental and computational studies, this work lays a strong foundation for the rational design of state-of-the-art photocatalysts. The versatility of BiVO_4 in multi-functional roles, coupled with strategies such as morphology control, doping, heterostructure formation, and oxygen vacancy engineering, demonstrates its adaptability for various applications, including wastewater treatment, CO_2 reduction, and green ammonia production. Despite significant advancements, challenges such as low solar-to-chemical conversion efficiency, limited long-term stability, and difficulty in achieving industrial-scale applications persist.

From a future perspective, several research directions emerge as critical for addressing these challenges and advancing BiVO_4 -based photocatalysis:

1. Industrial wastewater treatment: Investigating modified BiVO_4 photocatalysts for real industrial wastewater, which presents a more complex and challenging matrix than synthetic wastewater, is essential. Emphasis should be placed on understanding the formation and toxicity of intermediate degradation products, particularly persistent pollutants like pesticides and forever chemicals.

2. Photocatalyst optimization: Advanced strategies such as nanostructuring, facet-oriented growth, and doping with transition metals or semiconductors need further exploration. Single-atom catalysis (SAC) remains underexplored for BiVO_4 -based systems and offers a promising approach for enhancing catalytic activity and reducing material costs. Using non-noble single atoms can enhance catalytic activity while lowering material costs, making this approach highly attractive for sustainable and efficient photocatalysis. Stabilizing catalyst morphology and preventing deactivation will also be crucial for long-term commercial applications. Despite the extensive research on Z-scheme and dual

Z-scheme heterojunction photocatalysis, a comprehensive discussion on the charge transfer mechanism considering critical electronic parameters—such as Fermi level positioning, valence band, and conduction band alignment—is still required. Understanding these parameters is essential for elucidating the underlying charge carrier dynamics and optimizing the efficiency of photocatalytic and PEC processes.

3. Hybrid systems and natural sunlight utilization: Designing hybrid solar photocatalyst systems that integrate seamlessly with existing wastewater treatment technologies is a priority. Shifting from artificial light sources to natural sunlight for photocatalytic studies is imperative for realistic and geographically adaptable applications. Furthermore, recovery techniques, such as substrate-supported photocatalysts, can facilitate practical implementation.

4. CO₂ reduction and renewable energy applications: Developing strategies to enhance the selectivity of CO₂ reduction products, particularly multi-carbon (C₂₊) hydrocarbons, is a critical avenue. Integrating renewable energy sources like solar and wind and photocatalytic CO₂ reduction can lead to sustainable production of high-value fuels and chemicals. Coupling reduction with oxidation reactions (e.g., water oxidation) and employing machine learning (ML) tools for catalyst design and optimization will accelerate advancements in this field.

5. Water splitting and hydrogen production: In the domain of PEC water splitting, novel synthesis techniques, cocatalyst development, and interfacial engineering are pivotal for improving photoelectric conversion efficiency. Addressing stability issues, such as photocorrosion in BiVO₄-based materials, through strategies like anti-passivation layers and device structure modifications, is critical. Integrated with PV-EC technology, wireless PEC systems, and artificial leaves hold promise for scalable and sustainable hydrogen production.

6. Reaction mechanisms investigation and by-products: Future research should prioritize in-depth studies on reaction mechanisms and by-product formation during photodegradation, focusing on optimizing the BiVO₄ photocatalytic pathway. Advanced *in-situ* spectroscopic techniques such as Raman, FTIR, VB-XPS, and UPS can offer valuable insights into charge transfer processes and electronic structures, aiding the development of more efficient photocatalytic systems. Additionally, addressing specific knowledge gaps and application challenges, such as strategies for selectively modulating reactive oxygen species generation, is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of photocatalysts in real-world water treatment applications.

7. Energy consumption studies: Comparative studies on the energy consumption of BiVO₄ photocatalytic decontamination systems versus other water treatment processes and BiVO₄-based fuel production systems versus other fuel generation processes are essential. Such analyses will provide valuable insights and help accelerate the adoption of BiVO₄-based technologies in practical applications.

In summary, BiVO₄-based materials exhibit exceptional promise across environmental remediation and renewable energy applications. By addressing the existing challenges and leveraging multidisciplinary approaches—including photocatalysis, computational modeling, advanced characterization techniques, and renewable energy integration—BiVO₄ can become a frontrunner in achieving sustainable and efficient solutions for global environmental and energy challenges. These efforts will significantly contribute to transitioning society toward a greener

and more sustainable future.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Author contribution statement

O. M.: Conceptualization, data curation, investigation, validation, writing – original draft. V. K.: Writing – original draft. K. P.: Writing – original draft. S. K.: Writing – review & editing. G. K.: Visualization. H. M.: Writing – review & editing. G. G.: Writing – review & editing, funding acquisition. B. S.: Writing – review & editing. J. K.: Writing – review & editing, funding acquisition. R. D.: Writing – review & editing. D. D.: Project administration, funding acquisition, supervision. A. K.: Project administration, funding acquisition, supervision, resources. All authors have reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Use of AI statement

None.

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